

Probabilistic Cataloging of the Globular Cluster Messier 2:
Improved PSF Photometry of Crowded Stellar Fields

Benjamin Charles Germain Lee

Advisor: Douglas Finkbeiner, Professor of Astronomy and of Physics, Harvard University

A thesis presented to the Department of Astronomy in partial fulfillment of the
requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Arts

April 7, 2017
Harvard College

In memory of S.J.P.G. '53

I believe that stars are the headlights of angels

driving from heaven to save us

to save us

Look in the sky

They're driving from heaven into our eyes

... final words are so hard to devise ...

- D.C. Berman

Personal Acknowledgments

I would like to thank a small subset of people who have changed my life in meaningful ways over the past four years, both at Harvard and elsewhere:

Professor Finkbeiner: working on probabilistic cataloging over the past two years under your guidance has proven time and time again to be the highlight of my time at Harvard. It is difficult for me to articulate the extent of my gratitude for your countless hours of mentorship – you have genuinely changed my life. I have learned so much working with you, and your kindness, generosity, insightfulness, and infectious love of astrophysics will forever be appreciated.

Stephen: when I first began working with you, I never could have imagined that I would be so fortunate to have such an intelligent, kind, and thoughtful graduate student as a mentor. Without you, this thesis would not have been possible. Thank you for all of our meetings and discussions over the past two years. More importantly, thank you for being a true friend.

Tansu, Kiefer, and the rest of the Finkbeiner group: thank you for the wonderful experience of working with you. Your input and feedback on probabilistic cataloging has been invaluable.

Professor Charbonneau and the Astronomy 99 class: thank you for your incredible support and feedback. I enjoyed learning from all of you, and I will truly miss our class meetings.

Professor Siemiginowska and Josh: as my external readers, thank you for all of your thoughtful and thorough comments, as well as for helping me to shape this document into its final form.

Professor Eisenstein: thank you for all of your invaluable guidance over the past three years.

Tamás: thank you for being such a formative influence in my love of research. Your generosity has opened incredible doors for me, and I will forever be grateful for all that you have taught me over the past six years.

Saahil: what a ride these past four years have been. I couldn't be prouder to call you my brother.

Mentors: Prof. Amitabh Basu, Prof. Warren Goldfarb, Prof. Girma Hailu, Prof. Lars Hernquist, Prof. Kevin Madigan, Prof. Gabriel Pizzorno & Dr. Richard Wilton

Eliot House Tutors: Marion Dierickx & Val Bolotnyy

McDonogh Teachers: Mr. Abbot, Mr. Conn, Mr. Grega, Mr. Hudson, Mr. Shang & Ms. Wender

Friends: Amy Huang, Andrew White, Ashvin Swaminathan, Asad Khan, Ben Sorscher, Blake Paterson, David Cromwell, Elgin Gulpinar, Ethan Brodsky, Evan Sandhoefner, Francesca Childs, Greg Parker, Ian Grant, Jackie Martinez, Jay Brooks, Kathryn Klinge, Luke Ross, Matt Brown, Mengting Zhang, Ryan Kerr, Stephen Mackereth, & Vishnu Razdan

And lastly, my family:

Oma: you are my inspiration.

Mom & Dad: I love you both more than I could ever express. Thank you for everything.

XIII

It was evening all afternoon.

It was snowing

And it was going to snow.

The blackbird sat

In the cedar-limbs.

- Wallace Stevens

SUBMITTED APRIL 7, 2017

Typeset using L^AT_EX **modern** style in AAS_TE_X61

Contents

1. Abstract	9
2. Introduction I: Cataloging	10
2.1. Cataloging	11
2.2. Aperture Photometry	13
2.3. PSF Photometry	13
2.4. DAOPHOT	14
3. Introduction II: Probabilistic Cataloging	18
3.1. Bayesian Inference	18
3.2. Probabilistic Cataloging	20
3.3. Markov Chain Monte Carlo	22
3.4. Metropolis-Hastings Algorithm	22
3.5. Reversible-jump Markov Chain Monte Carlo	23
3.6. Diffusive Nested Sampling	25
4. Methodology I: The Implementation of Probabilistic Cataloging	26
4.1. Specification of Model Parameters	26
4.2. Priors	27
4.3. Likelihood	29
4.4. MCMC Proposals	30
4.5. Tuning Parameters	31
4.6. Assessing Convergence	33
5. Methodology II: Test Conditions for Comparing Cataloging Algorithms	35
5.1. Sloan Digital Sky Survey	35
5.2. Test Image	36
5.3. Motivations for the Test Image Choice: Comparison Catalogs & Beyond	38

	7
6. Results I: The Catalog Ensemble	41
6.1. Depicting the Catalog Ensemble	41
6.2. Quantifying Performance: Completeness & False Discovery Rate	44
6.3. Residuals	46
7. Condensed Catalog	55
7.1. Labeling Procedure	55
7.2. Quantifying Crowding: Sigma Factor (sigfac)	58
8. Results II: The Condensed Catalog	64
8.1. Completeness & False Discovery Rate	64
8.2. Cuts on Sigfac	65
9. Results III: Response to Different Seeing Conditions	73
9.1. Data Reduction of Exposures	73
9.2. Completeness, False Discovery Rate, and Beyond	74
10. Discussion & Conclusion	85
10.1. Improving Runtime	86
10.2. Other Future Work	90
10.3. Toward Future Survey Pipelines	92
11. Appendix	94
11.1. Determining f_{min}	94
11.2. Sparse Field Validation of Probabilistic Cataloging	100
11.3. Convergence Statistics	103
11.4. Derivation of Flux Sigfac	106
11.5. Derivation of Position Sigfac	109
12. Science Acknowledgments	113

A Note about Collaboration

Many of the central results of my thesis research coincide with the results that appear in a manuscript by Stephen Portillo, Professor Finkbeiner, Tansu Daylan, and myself (I am second author on the manuscript). This manuscript was submitted to the *Astronomical Journal* on March 3, 2017, and can be viewed at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1703.01303>. My primary contributions during my thesis research include the development of metrics and other methods for assessing catalog performance, as well as the development of the labeling procedure for distilling a catalog ensemble to a condensed catalog and the analysis of probabilistic cataloging's response to different seeing conditions. In addition, I contributed to the collective work on the sigfac parameters for the condensed catalog, as well as the different f_{min} runs and the sparse field validation.

All of the writing that appears in this thesis was written by me specifically for the purpose of this thesis. The few sentences that appear verbatim in the manuscript were added by me *after* having written the passages for my thesis. Furthermore, I produced all 41 figures in this thesis, with the exception of Figure 16 in Chapter 7, Figure 23 in Chapter 8, and Figures 36 & 37 in the Appendix. These 4 figures were produced by Stephen Portillo for the manuscript. With the exception of these figures, all of the figures that appear in both this thesis and the manuscript were produced by me as part of my thesis work.

1. ABSTRACT

Cataloging is an essential part of the data processing pipelines of modern surveys: most astrophysicists conduct research using catalogs of astronomical objects rather than raw telescope images. Though traditional cataloging packages perform well in most instances, crowded fields are particularly challenging due to the blending of and covariance between neighboring sources. With the improved depth of future telescope surveys, the fraction of exposures in the crowded limit will only continue to increase. As a result, it is more important than ever to explore new methods of crowded field photometry. In this thesis, I present the first application of probabilistic cataloging to real optical data. Probabilistic cataloging uses Bayesian inference and a trans-dimensional search to sample the space of all possible catalogs consistent with an image, producing an ensemble of catalogs instead of just one. Unlike catalogs produced by traditional cataloging packages, the resulting catalog ensemble retains fully marginalized deblending uncertainties and covariances between sources.

I quantitatively show that probabilistic cataloging outperforms DAOPHOT, the best-performing of the traditional stellar photometry packages in the crowded limit, on a 100×100 pixel cutout of a Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) r -band image of the globular cluster Messier 2 (Becker et al. 2007). Adopting a Hubble Space Telescope catalog of the same region of sky as ground truth, I show that the catalog ensemble generated using probabilistic cataloging is complete to over 1 magnitude deeper than the corresponding DAOPHOT catalog while maintaining a similar false discovery rate. Additional tests show that probabilistic cataloging is robust to different seeing conditions. Lastly, I provide a labeling procedure by which the catalog ensemble can be distilled to a single “condensed” catalog with fully marginalized uncertainties that maintains a similar completeness and false discovery rate to those of the catalog ensemble. These results demonstrate the applicability of probabilistic cataloging to future surveys such as the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope.

2. INTRODUCTION I: CATALOGING

Much astrophysical research relies not on telescope images directly but rather on catalogs of astronomical objects generated using these images. Consequently, the process of mapping an image to a corresponding catalog containing the position and flux of each source is essential to modern astrophysics. With the advent of charge-coupled devices (CCDs) and modern computers, the process of cataloging stellar fields is now reserved exclusively for computer packages such as DAOPHOT, DOPHOT, SExtractor, and the Sloan Digital Sky Survey Photo package (Stetson et al. 1987; Schechter 1993; Bertin & Arnouts 1996; Lupton et al. 2001). Such packages are central components of the data-processing pipelines of large surveys, as evidenced by Photo.

While these packages are capable of performing photometry and astrometry both quickly and to a relatively high degree of accuracy in most fields, these algorithms begin to fail in the limit of crowded stellar fields. The most common failure mode is failing to deblend overlapping sources properly.

Furthermore, the improved depth of future telescopes such as the Large Synoptic Space Telescope (LSST) will lead to most images being in the “crowded field” limit. As the demands of surveys will only continue to increase, these traditional photometry algorithms will no longer be sufficient: in an investigation of potential photometry algorithms for the LSST pipeline, Becker et al. (2007) found that all traditional algorithms consistently fall short by a factor of 2-3 according to the Science Requirements Document specifications for point spread function (PSF) photometry. Alternative photometry algorithms for cataloging crowded fields are thus crucial to future surveys.

One such photometry algorithm is known as *probabilistic cataloging*. Probabilistic cataloging was first conceived by Peter Green (Green 1995) and applied to mock data in the context of astronomy by Brendon Brewer, Daniel Foreman-Mackey, and David Hogg (Brewer et al. 2013; Brewer 2015a). It differs from traditional cataloging programs in a fundamental way: while traditional cataloging programs produce a *single* deterministic catalog of stars per image by imposing hard decisions such as strict signal-to-noise cuts

for source detection, probabilistic cataloging aims to produce an *ensemble* of catalogs by sampling the space of all possible catalogs consistent with an image. Doing so avoids the hard cuts imposed by traditional cataloging algorithms when creating only one deterministic catalog (Brewer et al. 2013). Statistics related to hyperparameters can then be computed by marginalizing over the ensemble of catalogs, and the ensemble of catalogs retains fully marginalized uncertainties over covariant neighbors.

In this chapter, I introduce cataloging. In Chapter 3, I introduce probabilistic cataloging, as well as its underlying formalism. In Chapter 4, I describe the specific implementation of probabilistic cataloging adopted for this thesis. In Chapter 5, I describe the test conditions used to quantify the performances of probabilistic cataloging and DAOPHOT. In Chapter 6, I present results comparing the performance of probabilistic cataloging to that of DAOPHOT. In Chapter 7, I provide a labeling procedure for distilling the catalog ensemble to a single “condensed” catalog. In Chapter 8, I present results quantifying the performance of this condensed catalog. In Chapter 9, I present results testing probabilistic cataloging’s response to different seeing conditions. Lastly, in Chapter 10, I provide a discussion of the results and conclude the thesis.

2.1. Cataloging

Given a single telescope image, I define a “catalog” \mathcal{C} as the set of positions and fluxes of detected sources in the image:

$$\mathcal{C} = \{x_i, y_i, f_i\}_{i=1}^N \quad (1)$$

where source positions $\{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ in the catalog can be recorded in any number of coordinate systems, such as equatorial coordinates (i.e., right ascension and declination) or image coordinates,¹ and the fluxes $\{f_i\}_{i=1}^N$ of the sources are most often recorded in units corresponding to the detector. Given this definition, cataloging is thus the process of determining the positions and fluxes of sources in an image.

¹ In general, the desired final coordinate system for the positions of catalog sources is any choice of sky coordinates, such as equatorial coordinates. The use of pixel coordinates is simply a convenient intermediate step, assuming that the coordinate transformation from pixel to sky coordinates is possible and can be implemented. For our purposes, I assume that this is the case.

Understanding the process of cataloging is essential to astrophysical research because the final output of modern survey pipelines is in catalog form, and most astrophysical research is performed on these catalogs as opposed to the telescope images themselves. The reasons for this are manifold. For example, catalogs are a useful data format for studying large populations of astronomical objects, such as calculating the 2-point correlation function (Eisenstein et al. 2005). Catalogs are also well-suited for studying sub-populations, such as selecting stars with certain colors. Most practically, however, the volume of raw telescope data makes it infeasible for every researcher to process raw exposures in order to conduct research, thereby making catalogs the only real alternative sources of information (Annunziatella et al. 2012).

Although most astrophysical research is performed on catalogs of celestial objects, rather than telescope images from which they are derived, catalogs are *not* the fundamental output of astrophysical research (Brewer et al. 2013). Rather, catalogs are an intermediate step, and any error introduced in cataloging is passed downstream to this data product. Both the determination of source positions (i.e., astrometry) and the determination of source fluxes (i.e., photometry) are methods extrinsic to the images themselves and inevitably result in information loss when mapping from image space to catalog space. Although astrometry and photometry concern themselves with minimizing the information loss in this mapping, the information loss can be just as detrimental to modern astrophysical research as a malfunctioning CCD or poor atmospheric conditions. Phrased alternatively, the resulting catalogs with which astrophysicists perform research are less faithful representations of the true imaged sources, and improvements to photometry can be just as powerful as more observation time or direct improvements to an imaging device.^{2,3}

² Although astrometry and photometry refer to two separate processes, most traditional photometry packages perform astrometry and photometry simultaneously. For this reason, I will use the term photometry to refer to both flux determination and position determination throughout this thesis.

³ Because the central focus of this thesis is the application of probabilistic cataloging to stellar fields, I will limit the following discussion to stellar photometry.

2.2. Aperture Photometry

Astrophysicists currently rely on two forms of photometry using CCD images: aperture photometry and PSF photometry. Aperture photometry is the simpler of the two methods to perform. It entails calculating a source's intensity by computing the sum of the pixel values in a region containing the source and subtracting off an estimate of the sky background contribution in the region (Laher et al. 2012). This is often accomplished by measuring the flux in concentric circles around the star of interest, where the flux in the outermost annulus is used to determine the sky background. Although this method is robust in the case of normal stellar fields, it hinges upon the ability to measure the sky background contribution near the star in question without suffering from contamination by nearby stars. Thus, crowded stellar fields present significant complications to aperture photometry as formulated.

2.3. PSF Photometry

Astrophysicists instead employ PSF photometry in the crowded limit. A point spread function (PSF) is a model of the response of an imaging device to a point source. In the context of stellar photometry, the imaging device is a CCD, and a star is modeled as a point source.⁴ The PSF is a convolution of seeing, optical contribution, and pixel response. For ground-based telescopes, seeing is the primary contributor to the PSF (Romanishin 2006).

For the purposes of this thesis, I define the PSF as a function $\mathcal{P} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that maps a pixel coordinate (l, m) to a scalar value $\mathcal{P}(l - x_i, m - y_i)$, where (x_i, y_i) is the position of the center of star i and

$$\sum_{\substack{(l,m) \in \text{pixel} \\ \text{coordinates}}} \mathcal{P}(l - x_i, m - y_i) = 1 \quad (2)$$

When multiplied by the star's flux, this scalar value $\mathcal{P}(l - x_i, m - y_i)$ represents the star's pixel-convolved flux contribution at the point (l, m) . This function is thus a generative model: it can be used to map a catalog of sources to a model image, where the value λ_{lm} of

⁴ Significantly, galaxies are *extended* sources and thus cannot be modeled as point sources.

the (l, m) th pixel is calculated as:

$$\lambda_{lm} = \sum_{i=1}^N f_i \mathcal{P}(l-x_i, m-y_i) \quad (3)$$

where f_i is the flux of star i .

PSF photometry concerns itself with the determination of a catalog that best models the observed image by comparing the observed image to a model image using a metric that quantitatively captures the notion of how “well” a model image resembles the observed image. Given that the number of sources in the observed image is unknown, both the choice of metric itself and the method of minimization convergence differ between algorithms. To illustrate examples of these choices, I will next describe the implementation of DAOPHOT, a popular PSF photometry algorithm.

2.4. DAOPHOT

DAOPHOT, currently available in its second version, DAOPHOT II, was first made available in 1986 (Stetson et al. 1987). In the crowded field limit, DAOPHOT outperforms DOPHOT, SExtractor, and the SDSS Photo package (Becker et al. 2007).^{5,6} It was designed specifically for stellar photometry and therefore does not differentiate between stars and galaxies (Becker et al. 2007). The package contains a number of functions that enable the user to create a single catalog. DAOPHOT’s functions include:⁷

1. **FIND**: identifies stars above a user-defined σ detection threshold relative to the local sky brightness. In brief, this is accomplished by iterating over each pixel in the image and performing a least-squares fit of a Gaussian of width δ within a neighborhood around the selected pixel, where δ is the user’s best estimate of the FWHM of the PSF at the time of using the function (Stetson et al. 1987). The algorithm automatically identifies and removes bad pixels from the fit.

⁵ Because DAOPHOT is the most accurate of these packages in the crowded limit, it serves as the best example of traditional cataloging packages for later comparison with probabilistic cataloging. I will directly compare probabilistic catalogs with DAOPHOT catalogs in later chapters.

⁶ For a description of DOPHOT, I direct the reader to Schechter (1993), Davis (1994), and Ferrarese et al. (2000); for a description of SExtractor, I direct the reader to Bertin & Arnouts (1996) and Annunziatella et al. (2012); and for a description of the SDSS imaging pipeline, I direct the reader to Lupton et al. (2001).

⁷ Unless explicitly cited, the following information is from Stetson (1998).

2. **PHOTOMETRY**: performs approximate aperture photometry using a star list produced from the first iteration of **FIND** and up to 12 user-specified aperture radii.
3. **PICK**: picks a subset of stars for more accurate aperture photometry, given a star list, fitting radius, and PSF radius (Becker et al. 2007). This function removes stars too close to the edge of the image, as well as stars near brighter stars or saturated stars. **PICK** returns a list of the remaining stars up to the number of stars requested by the user.
4. **PSF**: evaluates the PSF using a list of stars. Currently, **PSF** returns the best-fit of the following functions:
 - (a) A bivariate Gaussian (2 parameters)
 - (b) A bivariate Lorentz function (3 parameters)
 - (c) A "Moffat function" (3 parameters)
 - (d) A "Penny function" (5 parameters)
5. **GROUP**: partitions the identified stars into equivalence classes of stars with overlapping brightness profiles for simultaneous PSF fitting. It identifies this "critical overlap" via the following procedure: for any pair of stars, the location of the fainter star is fixed, and the flux of the brighter star is evaluated. If this flux exceeds the "critical overlap" parameter multiplied by the random error per pixel, then the stars are grouped together. This "critical overlap" parameter must be tuned to the dataset by the user such that the groups are all smaller than 60 in number.
6. **NSTAR**: performs simultaneous PSF photometry of stars in the equivalence classes determined by **GROUP**. This function is iterative and is run a maximum of 50 times for convergence.
7. **SUBSTAR**: removes the PSF profiles of stars identified in **NSTAR** from the original image, leaving a residual image that can then be processed by these functions again.

8. ALLSTAR: performs the equivalent of GROUP, NSTAR, and SUBSTAR on all stars simultaneously. This function is preferred by [Stetson \(1998\)](#).

These functions are then used in an iterative fashion in order to develop a stellar catalog. The implementation used by [Becker et al. \(2007\)](#) in their tests for the LSST pipeline is presented in pseudocode in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 [Becker et al. \(2007\)](#)'s Implementation of DAOPHOT

Run: FIND to find bright stars
Run: PHOTOMETRY to find an initial PSF (using a purely analytic PSF model)
Run: ALLSTAR to generate an initial catalog with positions, brightnesses, and local sky values
Improve: the PSF accuracy by increasing the PSF complexity to include a lookup table
Do:
Run: PSF on the full image, not residuals
Reject: stars based on an RMS cut
While: convergence has not yet been reached, or fewer than 3 iterations have been performed
Run: ALLSTAR again to update the catalog
Improve: the PSF accuracy once more by adding linear spatial variation to the PSF lookup table
Repeat: the PSF improvement loop in lines 5-9
Run: FIND on the residual image to find blended neighbors
Run: ALLSTAR to perform joint photometry
Run: SUBSTAR to remove only neighbors
Improve: the PSF accuracy by adding quadratic spatial variation to the PSF lookup table
Reject: stars based on an RMS cut
Run: FIND on the full image with the final FWHM from the PSF
Run: ALLSTAR for photometry and object subtraction
Run: FIND on the residuals to identify blended and faint objects
Run: ALLSTAR on the full catalog up to this point
Run: FIND on the updated residuals
Run: ALLSTAR for a final catalog

Because traditional cataloging packages such as DAOPHOT perform well on most stellar fields, the disadvantages of the packages are oftentimes overlooked. However, in the case of crowded stellar fields, these peak-finding algorithms that rely on hard cuts can lead to catastrophic failure modes. For instance, the SDSS pipeline failed to produce *any* catalog for images of the center portion of the globular cluster Messier 2. Even in the case that these packages do successfully produce catalogs of crowded stellar fields, these catalogs often fail to deblend overlapping stars and properly identify faint ones. Moreover, these traditional cataloging packages cannot be scaled to run on an entire survey's crowded field exposures without frequent human intervention due to their modular nature and numerous hard-wired variables, as detailed at length by [Becker et al. \(2007\)](#). In order to resolve these

issues, alternative crowded field photometry algorithms must be considered for present and future surveys.

3. INTRODUCTION II: PROBABILISTIC CATALOGING

Probabilistic cataloging represents an alternative approach to cataloging stellar fields. The fundamental distinction between it and traditional cataloging methods arises from the fact that it uses Bayesian inference and a trans-dimensional search to sample the space of all possible catalogs.⁸ Sampling the posterior distribution results in an *ensemble* of catalogs consistent with an image. By creating an ensemble of catalogs, this method provides a probabilistic alternative to the hard cuts (e.g., σ detection thresholds) introduced in the traditional cataloging packages to create one deterministic catalog. Furthermore, the catalog ensemble retains fully marginalized uncertainties, including deblending uncertainties and covariances between neighboring sources.

I will now introduce the theory behind probabilistic cataloging, first formalized in the context of astronomy by [Brewer et al. \(2013\)](#). Because probabilistic cataloging is formulated within a Bayesian framework, an understanding of Bayesian inference is essential to understanding probabilistic cataloging and its differences from traditional cataloging software. For this reason, I begin by introducing Bayesian inference.

3.1. Bayesian Inference

I begin with a proof of Bayes' Theorem, the central tenet of Bayesian inference. Let A be a proposition, let \bar{A} be the negation of the proposition, and let $\mathbb{P}(A)$ be the probability of A being true. From the Principle of Non-Contradiction, it follows that either A is true or \bar{A} is true, and thus, we arrive at the *sum rule*:

$$\mathbb{P}(A) + \mathbb{P}(\bar{A}) = 1 \quad (4)$$

We define $\mathbb{P}(A, B)$ as the *joint probability* of A and B being true and $\mathbb{P}(A|B)$ as the *conditional probability* of A being true given B being true. By definition,

$$\mathbb{P}(A|B) = \frac{\mathbb{P}(A, B)}{\mathbb{P}(B)} \quad (5)$$

⁸ Indeed, Bayesian inference is a powerful tool for crowded fields in general. For example, [Primini & Kashyap \(2014\)](#) applied Bayesian inference to X-ray photometry in the crowded limit, and [Budavári & Basu \(2016\)](#) applied Bayesian inference to the problem of cross-matching sources in crowded fields. Probabilistic cataloging specifically has been successfully applied to gamma-ray data ([Daylan et al. 2016](#)).

for $\mathbb{P}(B) > 0$. From this, the *product rule* immediately follows:

$$\mathbb{P}(A, B) = \mathbb{P}(A|B)\mathbb{P}(B) \quad (6)$$

Because the joint probability of A and B is the same as the joint probability of B and A , $\mathbb{P}(A, B) = \mathbb{P}(B, A)$. It follows from the product rule that:

$$\mathbb{P}(A|B)\mathbb{P}(B) = \mathbb{P}(A, B) = \mathbb{P}(B, A) = \mathbb{P}(B|A)\mathbb{P}(A) \quad (7)$$

Re-arranging the outermost equality, it follows that:

$$\mathbb{P}(B|A) = \frac{\mathbb{P}(A|B)\mathbb{P}(B)}{\mathbb{P}(A)} \quad (8)$$

This is *Bayes' Theorem*.⁹ In particular, we are interested in the case that A is observed data, which I denote d , and B is our hypothesis, which I denote H (Trotta 2008). This formulation of Bayes' Theorem thus becomes:

$$\mathbb{P}(H|d) = \frac{\mathbb{P}(d|H)\mathbb{P}(H)}{\mathbb{P}(d)} \quad (9)$$

The power in Bayes' Theorem is that it provides a method for calculating *the posterior* $\mathbb{P}(H|d)$: the probability of the hypothesis H after incorporating the known data d . Bayesian inference allows us to update the probability of H as data are obtained. Here, $\mathbb{P}(H)$ is known as *the prior*: our prior belief of our hypothesis of H without knowledge of the data d . In the discrete case, $\mathbb{P}(d)$ is simply the sum of the joint probabilities of d and H for all outcomes of H :

$$\mathbb{P}(d) = \sum_H \mathbb{P}(d, H) = \sum_H \mathbb{P}(d|H)\mathbb{P}(H) \quad (10)$$

Because this is a sum of probabilities over all possible H 's, we can marginalize over H , and the term $\mathbb{P}(d)$ is effectively a normalization constant that can be ignored.¹⁰ Thus,

$$\mathbb{P}(H|d) \propto \mathbb{P}(d|H)\mathbb{P}(H) \quad (11)$$

⁹ Here, I assume that $\mathbb{P}(A) > 0$.

¹⁰ This is not true in the case of trans-dimensional searches, which will be introduced later in this chapter. In the case of trans-dimensional searches, the term on the denominator must be retained.

We can now generalize this framework with random variables and discrete hypotheses to one with continuous parameter distributions and probability density functions.¹¹ Let θ be a collection of unknown parameters, and let x be unknown data.¹² Furthermore, suppose that we have a prior probability distribution for θ , denoted $\mathbb{P}(\theta)$, where this modeled probability distribution has been created independently of x . Lastly, let $\mathbb{P}(x|\theta)$ be a model for how the probability distribution of x can be constructed given the parameters θ . Applying the formulation of Bayes' Theorem in equation (11), we find that:

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta|x) \propto \mathbb{P}(\theta)\mathbb{P}(x|\theta) \quad (12)$$

In the case of a specific dataset x^* , such as a specific telescope exposure, x in the above expression can be evaluated at x^* :

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta|x = x^*) \propto \mathbb{P}(\theta)\mathbb{P}(x|\theta)|_{x=x^*} \quad (13)$$

$\mathbb{P}(x|\theta)|_{x=x^*}$ is called *the likelihood function* $\mathcal{L}(x = x^*; \theta)$, which expresses the probability of obtaining $x = x^*$ given θ . The expression can be re-written as:

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta|x = x^*) \propto \mathbb{P}(\theta)\mathcal{L}(x = x^*; \theta) \quad (14)$$

This is the crux of Bayesian inference: it reveals how the posterior distribution can be inferred from the prior and the likelihood function.

3.2. Probabilistic Cataloging

We now have a prescription for determining the conditional probability of a catalog given an image, assuming that the prior and likelihood functions are specified. In order to specify the prior and likelihood in this instance, however, we must first specify the parameter space. We define the parameter space to be the space of all possible catalogs, where each catalog θ is parametrized via:

$$\theta = \{N, \{x_i, y_i, f_i\}_{i=1}^N, \{\beta_j\}_{j=1}^m\} \quad (15)$$

¹¹ To avoid lengthy definitions of probability spaces $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$, I leave these definitions to the reader to look up.

¹² This notation has been adopted from [Brewer et al. \(2013\)](#).

where N is the number of sources, $\{x_i, y_i, f_i\}$ is the collection of positions and flux for source i in the catalog, and $\{\beta_j\}_{j=1}^m$ is a collection of m other parameters, such as ones related to the flux distribution. θ is thus a modified version of \mathcal{C} presented in equation (1):

$$\theta = \{N, \mathcal{C}, \{\beta_j\}_{j=1}^m\} \quad (16)$$

The inclusion of the extra parameters N and $\{\beta_j\}_{j=1}^m$ in θ is necessary for probabilistic cataloging to explore the full region of catalog space, as described in Section 3.3. Accordingly, I hereafter take the parametrized catalog to be θ , not \mathcal{C} .

Specifying the prior $\mathbb{P}(\theta)$ can be accomplished by specifying the prior of the individual parameters within θ under the *assumption* that the probabilities factor:¹³

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta) = \mathbb{P}(\{\beta_j\}_{j=1}^m) \mathbb{P}(N | \{\beta_j\}_{j=1}^m) \prod_{i=1}^N \mathbb{P}(x_i, y_i) \mathbb{P}(f_i | \{\beta_j\}_{j=1}^m) \quad (17)$$

The specification of these factored prior distributions is reserved for Section 4.1 in the Methodology because the choice of priors depends on the specific application of probabilistic cataloging, such as optical versus gamma-ray astronomy, and therefore must be tailored accordingly.

Similarly, the likelihood function $\mathcal{L}(x = x^*; \theta)$ can be specified. Given a PSF, equation (3) gives the mapping from a catalog to a model image. The likelihood can then be computed by comparing the pixel values in the model image to those of the observed image. The exact specification of the likelihood function is reserved for Section 4.3 in the Methodology.

Once specified, the prior and likelihood give us a way to get to the posterior $\mathbb{P}(\theta | x = x^*)$. The question of interest then becomes how to sample $\mathbb{P}(\theta | x = x^*)$. This can be accomplished via Markov chain Monte Carlo.

¹³ This independence assumption is only an approximation: binary stars, for instance, violate the independence as posed.

3.3. Markov Chain Monte Carlo

Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) is a class of algorithms that can be used to sample most types of functions and is particularly well-suited for sampling the posterior in Bayesian inference questions (MacKay 2003).

A discrete-time Markov Chain of length M is an ordered set of random variables $\{X^{(0)}, X^{(1)}, \dots, X^{(M-1)}\}$ such that:

$$\mathbb{P}(X^{(t+1)}|X^{(0)}, \dots, X^{(t)}) = \mathbb{P}(X^{(t+1)}|X^{(t)}), \quad 0 \leq t \leq M-2$$

(Trotta 2008). Markov chain Monte Carlo entails the construction of a Markov chain by stepping through parameter space, where, after each step in the chain, one or more of the parameters in θ are perturbed via a proposal distribution. This generates a proposal, or proposed step. The likelihood of the proposal is evaluated via the posterior and this new set of parameters. Then, according to a criterion or multiple criteria specified by the specific MCMC algorithm, the proposal is either accepted, in which case the likelihood is updated to the proposal's likelihood, or rejected. With a sufficient number of steps, the chain should accurately sample the posterior distribution.

Of particular importance in MCMC is the perturbation of parameters. MCMC algorithms require that detailed balance be preserved, meaning that for any two states θ and θ' ,

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta'|\theta)\mathbb{P}(\theta|x = x^*) = \mathbb{P}(\theta|\theta')\mathbb{P}(\theta'|x = x^*) \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbb{P}(\theta'|\theta)$ is the probability of transitioning from θ to θ' , and $\mathbb{P}(\theta|\theta')$ is the probability of transitioning from θ' to θ . (Fan & Sission 2010). With this established, it is now instructive to explore the Metropolis-Hastings Algorithm, a popular form of MCMC.

3.4. Metropolis-Hastings Algorithm

Let θ be the current state, and let θ' be the proposed state. Furthermore, let $g(\theta'|\theta)$ be the proposal distribution for proposing θ' given θ . The acceptance distribution $A(\theta'|\theta)$ is given by:

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta'|\theta) = g(\theta'|\theta)A(\theta'|\theta) \quad (19)$$

Substituting this into equation (18) in order to ensure that detailed balance is preserved, we find that:

$$g(\theta'|\theta)A(\theta'|\theta)\mathbb{P}(\theta|x=x^*) = g(\theta|\theta')A(\theta|\theta')\mathbb{P}(\theta'|x=x^*) \quad (20)$$

and thus,

$$\frac{A(\theta'|\theta)}{A(\theta|\theta')} = \frac{g(\theta|\theta')\mathbb{P}(\theta'|x=x^*)}{g(\theta'|\theta)\mathbb{P}(\theta|x=x^*)} \quad (21)$$

The Metropolis criterion is then the choice that:

$$A(\theta'|\theta) = \min \left(1, \frac{g(\theta|\theta')\mathbb{P}(\theta'|x=x^*)}{g(\theta'|\theta)\mathbb{P}(\theta|x=x^*)} \right) \quad (22)$$

The chain is then constructed by drawing an initial θ from the prior distribution, proposing a step θ' , accepting this proposal with probability $A(\theta'|\theta)$, and then repeating.

3.5. Reversible-jump Markov Chain Monte Carlo

Markov chain Monte Carlo as formulated in the previous sections handles the case of fixed-dimension parameter spaces. But what if θ itself contains an unknown number of parameters? [Green \(1995\)](#) provided the mathematical formalism for trans-dimensional Markov chain Monte Carlo, a form of MCMC that allows for the *number of parameters* to be fit for by the chain as well. In the case of such a trans-dimensional chain, another condition known as the “reversible-jump” condition must be satisfied: every time a parameter is added or removed, the move must be reversible; i.e., there must be a non-zero probability of the chain reversing this step. This is known as Reversible-jump Markov chain Monte Carlo. The trans-dimensionality of the chain is introduced via birth-death moves and split-merge moves.¹⁴

Reversible-jump MCMC is of particular importance to this thesis because probabilistic cataloging is contingent upon letting the number of sources in the catalog itself be a parameter, as seen in the inclusion of N in equation (15). Otherwise, fixed-dimension MCMC

¹⁴ For more thorough descriptions of the formalism behind Reversible-jump MCMC, I direct the reader to [Green \(1995\)](#), [Sambridge et al. \(2006\)](#), [Brewer et al. \(2010\)](#), and [Fan & Sission \(2010\)](#).

would have to be run over a wide range of N , which is problematic: this would cause a manifold increase in runtime, and analyzing evidence ratios of models with different values of N would be difficult in such a space.

In particular, probabilistic cataloging relies on birth-death moves in order to add and remove sources. Accordingly, I will derive the acceptance fraction for a birth move. Let θ be a catalog with N sources, and let u be a source with three parameters: $\{x_u, y_u, f_u\}$. Furthermore, let θ' be a catalog with $N+1$ sources equal to the catalog θ with the source u appended. We take $u' = \emptyset$. We observe that these parameters satisfy the dimensionality constraint that is required for a birth-death move:

$$\mathcal{D}(\theta) + \mathcal{D}(u) = \mathcal{D}(\theta') + \mathcal{D}(u') \quad (23)$$

where \mathcal{D} is the dimension operator (Green 1995; Daylan et al. 2016). The probability of the birth move adding the source u to the catalog θ is given by Green (1995):

$$A(\theta'|\theta) = \min \left(1, \frac{\mathbb{P}(\theta'|x=x^*)}{\mathbb{P}(\theta|x=x^*)} \frac{j(\theta')q(u')}{j(\theta)q(u)} \left| \frac{\partial(\theta', u')}{\partial(\theta, u)} \right| \right) \quad (24)$$

where $j(\theta)$ is the probability of proposing a birth step in state θ , $j(\theta')$ is the probability of proposing a death step in state θ' , $q(u)$ is the proposal probability distribution of u , and $q(u')$ is the proposal probability distribution of u' . In this case, the Jacobian evaluates to the identity matrix. Replacing the posterior with the likelihood and prior, we find that:

$$A(\theta'|\theta) = \min \left(1, \frac{\mathcal{L}(x=x^*|\theta')}{\mathcal{L}(x=x^*|\theta)} \frac{\mathbb{P}(\theta')}{\mathbb{P}(\theta)} \frac{j(\theta')q(u')}{j(\theta)q(u)} \right) \quad (25)$$

Because $u' = \emptyset$, $q(u') = 1$. Furthermore, we choose to take $j(\theta') = j(\theta)$ so that the probability of proposing a birth is equal to the probability of proposing a death. Using equation (17), the priors factor, reducing the previous equation to:

$$A(\theta'|\theta) = \min \left(1, \frac{\mathcal{L}(x=x^*|\theta')}{\mathcal{L}(x=x^*|\theta)} \frac{\mathbb{P}(N+1)}{\mathbb{P}(N)} \frac{\mathbb{P}(u)}{q(u)} \right) \quad (26)$$

Lastly, because we are free to choose $q(u)$ as long as $q(u)$ integrates to 1, we take $q(u) = \mathbb{P}(u)$ so that neither has to be computed for each birth-death move:

$$A(\theta'|\theta) = \min \left(1, \frac{\mathcal{L}(x = x^*|\theta') \mathbb{P}(N+1)}{\mathcal{L}(x = x^*|\theta) \mathbb{P}(N)} \right) \quad (27)$$

The acceptance fraction for a death move is then:

$$A(\theta|\theta') = \min \left(1, \frac{\mathcal{L}(x = x^*|\theta) \mathbb{P}(N)}{\mathcal{L}(x = x^*|\theta') \mathbb{P}(N+1)} \right) \quad (28)$$

3.6. Diffusive Nested Sampling

For the implementation of probabilistic cataloging used for this thesis, I adopt Diffusive Nested Sampling (DNS), a Monte Carlo variant of Nested Sampling first formalized by [Brewer et al. \(2010\)](#), as the sampler.¹⁵ It performs particularly well when the target distribution has many maxima, as is the case with probabilistic cataloging: because a catalog is invariant to the labeling of the sources, an N -source catalog with the highest posterior probability manifests itself as $N!$ degenerate maxima in the target distribution. Furthermore, DNS can be modified for Reversible-jump MCMC, as desired for probabilistic cataloging. For these reasons, the implementation of probabilistic cataloging central to this thesis relies upon DNS to sample the posterior distribution.

¹⁵ DNS modifies the target distribution by mixing the prior distribution with constrained forms of the prior distribution ([Brewer et al. 2013](#)). In particular, DNS first advances by creating levels, each of which is recursively defined as the e^{-1} quantile of likelihoods that have been stored by the chain in the previous level ([Brewer et al. 2010](#)). Thus, likelihood strictly increases as a function of level number. After creating a user-specified number of levels, DNS then samples a weighted sum of constrained distributions of each level (this differs from nested sampling, in which the chain samples the constrained distribution of only the highest level) ([Brewer et al. 2010](#)). By allowing the chain to explore these constrained distributions of lower levels, DNS is better-equipped to escape local maxima more easily. The technical details of DNS are better-suited for a paper on statistics, and for this reason, I have included only a brief overview of DNS. For more information on this method, I refer the reader to [Brewer et al. \(2010\)](#), [Brewer et al. \(2013\)](#), [Brewer \(2015a\)](#), and [Brewer & Foreman-Mackey \(2016\)](#).

4. METHODOLOGY I: THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PROBABILISTIC CATALOGING

In this chapter, I will describe the specific implementation of probabilistic cataloging adopted in this thesis, including a detailed description of the model space, priors, likelihood function, proposal distribution, tuning parameters, and methods of assessing convergence.

4.1. *Specification of Model Parameters*

The first step in specifying this implementation of probabilistic cataloging is to define fully the catalog parametrization θ in model space, which was introduced in equation (15) in Section 3.2 as:

$$\theta = \{N, \{x_i, y_i, f_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq N}, \{\beta_j\}_{j=1}^m\}$$

where N is the number of sources, $\{x_i, y_i, f_i\}$ is the collection of positions and flux for source i in the catalog, and $\{\beta_j\}_{j=1}^m$ is a collection of m other parameters that must be specified. In this implementation of probabilistic cataloging, the flux distribution is set to be a power law with a variable exponent α between a fixed minimum flux f_{min} and a variable maximum flux parameter f_{max} . Furthermore, we choose to fit for the isotropic background I_{sky} in order to model the sky background.¹⁶ Thus, in this implementation, $\{\beta_j\}_{j=1}^m$ is defined to be:

$$\{\beta_j\}_{j=1}^3 = \{\alpha, f_{max}, I_{sky}\} \quad (29)$$

such that:

$$\theta = \{N, \{x_i, y_i, f_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq N}, \{\alpha, f_{max}, I_{sky}\}\} \quad (30)$$

$\{\beta_j\}_{j=1}^m$ could contain a wide range of different parameters, such as a parametrization of the PSF of the image in order to fit for the PSF itself.¹⁷ In this implementation, however, we use the pixel-convolved PSF provided by the SDSS pipeline, which is described in Section 4.3.

¹⁶ I_{sky} is a nuisance parameter, as we marginalize over it.

¹⁷ Recall that DAOPHOT implements a variant of this, in that it fits for the PSF using various functional forms (this is described in detail in Section 2.4).

4.2. Priors

As described in Section 3.2, the prior $p(\theta)$ is completely characterized by the priors on the individual parameters under the assumption that the probabilities factor (Brewer et al. 2013). The priors on the individual parameters are specified as follows:

1. x_i and y_i are each given a uniform prior on the interval (0, 100) in units of pixels, corresponding to the bounds of the test image.¹⁸
2. f_i is drawn from the flux distribution set by f_{min} , f_{max} , and α , where the priors on f_{max} and α are enumerated next.
3. f_{max}^{-1} is given from a uniform prior on $(0, f_{bound}^{-1})$, where f_{bound} is taken to be no greater than the flux of the brightest source in the HST catalog. This definition of f_{bound} ensures that f_{max} is at least as large as the flux of the brightest point source. Although using the data to set the prior theoretically violates Bayesian principles, doing so is of little consequence here, as setting f_{max} anywhere between f_{bound} and ∞ has no appreciable effect on the resulting catalog ensemble for a reasonable choice of f_{bound} . Though we float f_{max} in this implementation, doing so is not necessary: one could fix f_{max} to be sufficiently high such that no star would ever have a flux exceeding f_{max} . f_{max} was included in this implementation simply because it was inherited from DNest3, Brendon Brewer’s code implementation of Diffusive Nested Sampling (Brewer 2016).
4. α^{-1} is given a uniform prior on the interval (0, 1). This prior is relatively uninformative but nonetheless gives greater weight to a power law exponent of -1 than to an exponent of -100 , as motivated by physics.
5. I_{sky} is given a log uniform prior with bounds of 300 ADU and 3000 ADU. The value of I_{sky} can be estimated to be within 10% of 1223 ADU by considering the sky mean and variance over the entire SDSS run excluding the 100×100 pixel region in ques-

¹⁸ For a description of the test image, I refer the reader to Chapter 5.

tion. Consequently, the bounds of 300 ADU and 3000 ADU are generous enough that there is no risk of the fit brushing against these bounds.¹⁹

6. N is given an exponential prior, which is motivated as follows. The number of point sources N is treated as the outcome of a Poisson process that would yield on average μ point sources. In this research, we are most interested in deblending statistically significant sources. Because the detection of faint sources is at best a second order contribution in aiding the deblending of brighter sources and because the computational evaluation time of the likelihood scales with N , we choose to adopt a prior on N that penalizes the addition of more point sources. The pixel counts are in the regime such that the problem can be approximated as a Gaussian process, so we use results from Gaussian statistics to motivate the functional form of the prior. In particular, the inclusion of an additional source improves the model by $3/2$ in log likelihood for a Gaussian problem, where $3/2$ arises from three factors of $1/2$, one for each of the three degrees of freedom (x_i, y_i, f_i) . Thus, to combat this increase in log likelihood, we have adopted a prior that incurs a penalty of $3/2$ in log likelihood for the addition of another source:

$$\log \pi(\mu + 1) - \log \pi(\mu) = -\frac{3}{2} \quad (31)$$

This motivates the choice of an exponential prior:

$$\pi(\mu) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{3}{2}\mu\right) \quad (32)$$

This exponential prior is given a lower bound of 0 and an upper bound of $N_{max} = 3000$.

¹⁹ This is verified in Section 11.3 of the Appendix.

4.3. Likelihood

In order to specify the likelihood function, it is first necessary to specify how a model image is calculated, given a catalog.²⁰ As described in Section 2.3, this is accomplished via the PSF.

CCDs measure counts in analog-to-digital converter units (ADU) equal to the number of photoelectrons multiplied by a gain factor. In the following discussion, we consider photoelectrons, as they are the Poisson-distributed quantity. Suppose the image is a rectangular grid of pixels with dimensions $W \times H$, such that the photoelectron count in pixel (l, m) is given by k_{lm} . Given the PSF \mathcal{P} ,²¹ we find that λ_{lm} , the expected count in pixel (l, m) , is given by:

$$\lambda_{lm} = I_{sky} + \sum_{i=1}^N f_i \mathcal{P}(l - x_i, m - y_i) \quad (33)$$

This equation is equivalent to equation (3), except that the sky background term has been added to this equation.

Because the pixel counts in the SDSS test image are sufficiently high, the noise can be assumed to be Gaussian distributed, but with an amplitude determined by Poisson statistics. We make this approximation to reduce the computational expense and are aware of the slight biases introduced. A more correct treatment would evaluate the full Poisson likelihood,²² but this is almost never done in optical astronomy. With this approximation, the likelihood function \mathcal{L} is given by:

$$\mathcal{L} = \prod_{l=1}^W \prod_{m=1}^H \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\lambda_{lm}}} \exp \left[-\frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2\lambda_{lm}} \right] \quad (34)$$

²⁰ This section follows analogously to Section 3.2 of [Portillo et al. \(2017\)](#). The implementation of probabilistic cataloging used in [Portillo et al. \(2017\)](#) is the same as the one used in this thesis.

²¹ For our selected SDSS test image, the SDSS pipeline provided a pixel-convolved PSF in the form of a 25×25 pixel grid. We then upsampled this $5 \times$ in each dimension using sinc interpolation, resulting in a 125×125 grid. To evaluate the contribution of a specific star to the model image, we then used the SciPy `interpolate.interp2d` function to interpolate the flux-multiplied PSF onto the model image using the star's coordinates (x_i, y_i) . There is a 5% mismatch between the PSF provided by the SDSS pipeline and the true PSF of the image, a consequence of the SDSS pipeline's confusion due to the extent of crowding in the field.

²² This is left for future work.

Because likelihood ratios suffice for MCMC sampling, it is useful to evaluate $\log \mathcal{L}$, in which case multiplicative constants can be ignored:

$$\log \mathcal{L} = \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H -\frac{1}{2} \log \lambda_{lm} - \frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2\lambda_{lm}} + C \quad (35)$$

Because it is much more computationally expensive to evaluate a logarithmic term than it is to evaluate just multiplicative and additive terms, the limiting term in computational complexity is the log term. Fortunately, the quadratic term is much more sensitive to changes in λ_{lm} , meaning that $\log \mathcal{L}$ can be approximated by ignoring the log term on the right-hand side of the equation:²³

$$\log \mathcal{L} \approx - \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2\lambda_{lm}} + C' \quad (36)$$

4.4. MCMC Proposals

We must also specify the proposals allowed in our MCMC implementation. The following list is from [Portillo et al. \(2017\)](#):

1. Choose a number of sources to perturb, and then perturb their positions and fluxes.
2. Perturb flux distribution parameters, changing all source fluxes to remain at the same quantile according to the perturbed parameters.²⁴
3. Perturb flux distribution parameters, keeping all source fluxes fixed.
4. Choose a number of sources to add to the catalog, and then add sources drawn from the prior with the current flux distribution parameters.
5. Choose a number of sources to remove, and then remove sources chosen at random from the catalog.

²³ The true effect of this term can be tested by running probabilistic cataloging both with and without this term. This is left for future work.

²⁴ In particular, the exponent of the flux distribution power law is perturbed, where the cumulative distribution function of each source in the flux distribution is preserved.

As described in Section 3.5, this implementation of probabilistic cataloging relies on Birth-death MCMC, a variant of Reversible-jump MCMC first formalized by Stephens (2000). Proposals of types 4 and 5 in the above list correspond to birth and death proposals, respectively.

Proposals perturbing components, proposals perturbing hyperparameters, and birth/death proposals are given equal probabilities of being selected, such that the probability of any of these proposal types being selected is $1/3$. Proposal types 2 and 3 in the above list (corresponding to proposals perturbing hyperparameters) are given equal probabilities of $1/6$, and proposal types 4 and 5 (corresponding to birth/death proposals) are given equal probabilities of $1/6$.

4.5. Tuning Parameters

I now present a list of all parameters in this implementation of probabilistic cataloging that require user input:

1. `N_max`, the upper bound on the prior on N
2. `f_min`, the lower bound on the flux distribution
3. `fmax_lo`, the lower bound on the prior on f_{max}
4. `f_norm`, the value at which $dN/d\log f$ is evaluated
5. `norm_lo`, the lower bound on norm ($dN/d\log f$)
6. `norm_hi`, the upper bound on norm
7. `background_lo`, the lower bound on the prior on I_{sky}
8. `background_hi`, the upper bound on the prior on I_{sky}
9. the penalty in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source

10. A number of parameters for `DNest3`, Brendon Brewer’s code implementation of Diffusive Nested Sampling (Brewer 2016):

- (a) the number of particles
- (b) the new level interval
- (c) the save interval
- (d) `threadSteps` - the number of steps each thread should execute independently before communication
- (e) the maximum number of levels
- (f) the backtracking scale length (λ in Brewer et al. (2010))
- (g) the strength of effect to force the histogram to equal push (β in Brewer et al. (2010))
- (h) the maximum number of saves

As described in Section 4.2, `background_lo` and `background_hi` can be set generously enough such that there is no risk of the fit brushing against them. The same is true for `N_max` and `fmax_lo`, as well as `f_norm`, `norm_lo`, and `norm_hi`.²⁵ Thus, the resulting catalog ensemble is robust to changes in these 7 parameters.

Furthermore, with the exception of the maximum number of levels parameter in `DNest3`, the `DNest3` parameters only affect the rate of convergence and memory usage. The maximum number of levels parameter in the `DNest3` implementation is more impactful, in that setting it too low prevents the chain from reaching the posterior peak. However, this can be circumvented by setting the number of levels to be generously high, with the only consequence being an increase in runtime.²⁶ Significantly, the `DNest3` implementation of MCMC is not necessary: Metropolis-Hastings can be used instead, thus avoiding these issues related to `DNest3` input parameters. Indeed, our initial tests using our own Metropolis-Hastings implementation indicated that it was slower than `DNest3`, but we

²⁵ The latter 3 variables impose a continuous log-uniform prior that serves as a proxy for a prior on the number of sources, thus avoiding having to set a discrete prior on the number of sources.

²⁶ This is described in more detail in Section 4.6.

now know that with a sufficiently clever proposal distribution, Metropolis-Hastings can be competitive.

This leaves two parameters of interest in the list: f_{min} and the penalty in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source. As described in Section 4.2, the choice of 3/2 for the penalty in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source is well-motivated. Nonetheless, in Section 11.1 of the Appendix, I present empirical results of experimentation with different values of both parameters.

4.6. Assessing Convergence

The question of convergence in the case of probabilistic cataloging is complicated by the fact that the chain is trans-dimensional. In particular, tests such as the Gelman and Rubin convergence diagnostic²⁷ cannot currently be applied to the catalog ensemble itself due to the labeling degeneracy described in Section 3.6. Although I present a procedure for labeling sources in Section 7.1, using this procedure to define a generalized Gelman and Rubin convergence diagnostic has been left for future work. Consequently, I adopt an alternative method of assessing convergence tailored specifically to Diffusive Nested Sampling (DNS).²⁸

In DNS, each level has a posterior weight equal to the prior multiplied by the likelihood. Even though each level is recursively defined as the e^{-1} quantile of likelihoods that have been stored by the chain in the previous level, the posterior weight is not monotonically increasing as a function of level number because the prior volume decreases as a function of level. Instead, the posterior weight achieves a maximum at a finite level number, called the “posterior peak.” The presence of this posterior peak can be taken as an indication of convergence.

Because DNS requires the maximum number of levels to be set by the user, there is no guarantee that the appearance of a posterior peak in the interval $[0, \text{max_level_number}]$ corresponds to the global maximum on the interval $[0, \infty)$. However, increasing the max-

²⁷ Along with the Geweke diagnostic, the Gelman and Rubin convergence diagnostic is one of the canonical tests of convergence for MCMC chains (Gelman & Rubin 1992; Cowles & Carlin 1996). Although it is not a perfect test, it is nonetheless a good test to first order.

²⁸ DNS was introduced in Section 3.6.

imum number of levels also increases runtime, which must be taken into consideration when setting the maximum number of levels parameter. In practice, this parameter is set empirically.²⁹

Even though the chain is trans-dimensional, the hyperparameters and pixels are of fixed dimension. Consequently, the Gelman and Rubin convergence diagnostic *can* be applied to these parameters (Cowles & Carlin 1996). In Section 11.3 of the Appendix, I present plots of the Gelman and Rubin convergence diagnostic for the pixels corresponding to the run adopted for analysis throughout the following chapters.

²⁹ After having analyzed many of these runs over the past 2 years, Stephen Portillo and I have developed some intuition for choosing the appropriate maximum number of levels.

5. METHODOLOGY II: TEST CONDITIONS FOR COMPARING CATALOGING ALGORITHMS

In order to show that probabilistic cataloging outperforms traditional cataloging algorithms on real optical data, it is necessary to establish appropriate test conditions under which the performances of the different cataloging algorithms can be quantified and compared. Accordingly, in this chapter, I will describe and motivate the test conditions chosen to make these comparisons.

5.1. *Sloan Digital Sky Survey*

For a test image, I selected a Sloan Digital Sky Survey image of the globular cluster Messier 2 (M2). The Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) is a photometric and spectroscopic survey that began collecting data in 2000 on an unprecedented scale for digital surveys, including performing multi-color photometry on half of the northern sky and performing spectroscopy on 10^6 galaxies and 10^5 quasars (Gunn et al. 1998). To date, there have been four iterations of SDSS (SDSS I - IV) and thirteen data releases. For more information regarding the latest SDSS data release, I direct the reader to Albareti et al. (2016).

Located at the Apache Point Observatory (APO) in Sunspot, New Mexico, the SDSS telescope is a 2.5m f/5 modified Ritchey-Chrétien wide-field altitude-azimuth telescope (York et al. 2000). The SDSS photometric camera comprises two arrays:³⁰

1. The photometric array, which consists of 30 2048×2048 SITE/Tektronix CCDs, is arranged in six columns of five CCDs each (Gunn et al. 1998). Each pixel is $24 \mu\text{m}$, corresponding to $0.396''$ on the sky (York et al. 2000).
2. The imaging array, used for astrometry, consists of 24 of the same CCDs. In particular, the imaging array aids astrometry by enabling bright astrometric stars to be mapped relative to objects of interest identified by the photometric array (Gunn et al. 1998).

³⁰ Because the central topic of this thesis is photometry, I limit my discussion to SDSS's photometric component.

The scan direction of the camera is along the columns of the photometric array. The CCDs in the photometric array are separated between rows, with a center-to-center separation of 91.0 mm, corresponding to $25.2'$ on the sky (York et al. 2000). The gaps resulting from this design are filled in by another strip, which is offset from the first strip by 93% of the width of the CCD. Filling in the gap either by a second scan or a strip in another run yields a stripe 2.54° wide (York et al. 2000; An et al. 2008). The camera images the sky at the sidereal rate by scanning along great circles (York et al. 2000). Each image has an effective exposure time of 54.1 seconds (An et al. 2008). The camera has five filters: u, g, r, i and z , with effective wavelengths of 349.8 nm, 462.7 nm, 613.9 nm, 746.7 nm, and 892.7 nm, respectively (Doi et al. 2010).

5.2. Test Image

For this particular test image, I selected a 100×100 pixel cutout of the SDSS r -band image of M2 from Data Release 12 with the following identification numbers in the SDSS Data Release 12 pipeline: run 2583, field 136, camcol 2 (Alam et al. 2015). This image has $1.05''$ seeing and is presented in Figure 1.

I extracted the 100×100 pixel cutout and the SDSS pipeline-generated PSF, as well as the astrometry, gain, bias, and counts-to-nanomaggies conversion, via the following procedure. The appropriate FITS files were obtained using the SDSS Data Release 12 website.³¹ I extracted the 100×100 pixel subregion from the idR file.³² I calibrated the astrometry of the image using the header of the frame file. Furthermore, I extracted the pixel-convolved PSF generated by the SDSS pipeline from the appropriate psField file. Lastly, I extracted the gain and bias for this subregion from the opECalib file by using the camcol, camrow, and pixel coordinates of the subregion, where I found the camrow in the frame file.

³¹ At the time of the submission of this thesis, the idR file could be downloaded at: data.sdss3.org/sas/dr12/env/PHOTO_DATA by selecting the appropriate field, camcol, run, and band. The frame file could be downloaded at: data.sdss3.org/fields by following the same procedure. The psField file could be downloaded at: data.sdss.org/sas/dr12/env/PHOTO_REDUX/301/ by selecting the appropriate run, then selecting the objcs folder, and lastly selecting the psField file for the appropriate camcol, field, and band. For a detailed description of these file types, I refer the reader to: <http://www.sdss.org/dr12/imaging/pipeline/>.

³² The exact pixel coordinates of the 100×100 cutout relative to the field in the idR FITS file are (640–740, 700–800).

Figure 1. Two stretches of the chosen test image, a 100×100 pixel cutout of the SDSS *r*-band image with the identification numbers: run 2583, field 136, camcol 2. The colorbar values are in units of ADU. The minimum and maximum pixel values in this 100×100 cutout are 1210 ADU and 28,050 ADU, respectively. The top plot is stretched according to these values, and the bottom plot is stretched to highlight the extent to which the field is crowded. The convention of pixels with higher counts appearing darker will be adopted throughout the rest of the chapters. In the bottom panel, a 20th magnitude star is labeled.

5.3. Motivations for the Test Image Choice: Comparison Catalogs & Beyond

The choice of this specific SDSS image of Messier 2 was motivated by the following factors. Located approximately 12.5 kpc away with a center at a right ascension and declination of 21h 33m 27.02s and $-00^{\circ} 49' 23.7''$, respectively, Messier 2 (M2) is a globular cluster with an extremely high stellar density: it contains approximately 150,000 stars and has a core radius of $0.34''$ (1.1 parsecs) and a half-light radius of $1.08''$ (3.6 parsecs) (Harris 1996). Consequently, any image of M2 is inherently an image of a crowded stellar field. In fact, this field is so crowded that the SDSS pipeline photometry package `PHOTO` failed to produce a catalog of this SDSS image of M2.

Furthermore, An et al. (2008) used this very same SDSS image, in conjunction with DAOPHOT, to produce a catalog of the corresponding portion of M2. Thus, I can directly compare the performances of probabilistic cataloging and DAOPHOT on the same test image with the same pixel values.³³ Because DAOPHOT performs the best among the traditional cataloging packages in the crowded limit, this comparison serves as a direct comparison of probabilistic cataloging with the most robust of the traditional cataloging packages (Becker et al. 2007). Significantly, exposures of the field *in all five bands* were used by An et al. (2008) in producing this catalog with DAOPHOT, whereas probabilistic cataloging uses only the *r*-band exposure as input, giving DAOPHOT an advantage in this regard.

M2 has also been imaged by the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) in the F606W band, and a catalog of M2 has been generated using these images as part of the Advanced Camera for Surveys (ACS) (Sarajedini et al. 2007; Anderson et al. 2008).³⁴ Significantly, HST has approximately 20 times the angular resolution of SDSS because HST is a space telescope and does not suffer from seeing due to atmospheric conditions, as does the ground-based

³³ Although I could have run DAOPHOT on the chosen image myself in order to produce a catalog for comparison, the An et al. (2008) catalog is advantageous. As described in Section 2.4, DAOPHOT requires the user both to set a number of tuning parameters and to determine the execution order of the main functions. An et al. (2008) were deliberate in the execution of DAOPHOT on this image, as detailed in Sections 3 and 4 of An et al. (2008). Therefore, I treat the An et al. (2008) catalog as representative of the best use case of DAOPHOT. Had I produced a catalog using DAOPHOT, the catalog would inevitably have been suboptimal, as I have no prior experience with the aforementioned subtleties of DAOPHOT.

³⁴ The specific F606W images used to generate this catalog consist of one 7 second exposure and four 140 second exposures, all of which were taken on May 2, 2006 (Anderson et al. 2008). These images are centered on a right ascension of 21h 33m 26s and a declination of $-00^{\circ} 49' 23''$ and are part of the dataset with the identification number j91952 (Anderson et al. 2008). The ACS Survey team generated this catalog of the central $2' \times 2'$ portion of M2 using “a sophisticated computer program that simultaneously analyzes all of the survey exposures for each cluster (one short exposure plus four to five deep exposures for each of the F606W and F814W filters),” where the exposures were taken by the Wide-Field Channel (WFC) of ACS onboard the HST (Anderson et al. 2008). For more information on the details of the automated photometry performed, I direct the reader to Anderson et al. (2008).

SDSS camera. Consequently, the HST ACS F606W-band catalog of M2 is more complete than any catalog derived from the SDSS image. For comparison, the HST ACS F606W-band catalog contains 6,051 sources in the region defined by the 100×100 pixel cutout of the selected SDSS image, while the DAOPHOT catalog identifies only 357 sources in the same region (the HST catalog identifies 1,049 sources brighter than 22nd magnitude alone). *Thus, the HST ACS F606W-band catalog can be treated as ground truth for comparison of the performance of probabilistic cataloging to that of DAOPHOT on the selected SDSS image.*³⁵

Moreover, M2 lies on Stripe 82, a 300 deg² stripe on the Celestial Equator that has been repeatedly imaged by SDSS in the *ugriz* bands for a number of reasons, including the detection of variable objects (Jiang 2014).³⁶ Because the exposures are subject to different seeing conditions, I can test the probabilistic cataloging’s response to information loss in the form of worse seeing. In addition, I can determine the worst seeing conditions for which probabilistic cataloging still outperforms the original DAOPHOT catalog as a method of quantifying the extent to which probabilistic cataloging outperforms DAOPHOT. Indeed, I devote Chapter 9 to these tests.

Lastly, a 100×100 pixel cutout is small enough that the computational runtime of the implementation of probabilistic cataloging adopted for this thesis is still reasonable. In addition, this specific 100×100 region was chosen because it is free of both saturated pixels and cosmic rays, eliminating further complications in the test conditions. Similarly, because M2’s stellar density is so high, the overwhelming majority of sources in the chosen image of M2 are stars, as opposed to galaxies. Therefore, the selected image is a suitable test case for comparing cataloging methods in the crowded limit without having to address the issue of differentiating stars from galaxies.³⁷

³⁵ The F606W filter is the closest of the HST filters to the SDSS *r* filter. The two filters are centered at similar wavelengths, but the HST F606W filter is much broader than the SDSS *r* filter. In addition, the AB_V magnitude system adopted by SDSS differs from the Vega magnitude system adopted by HST. With these factors considered, the HST and SDSS magnitudes of main sequence stars differ by of order a tenth of a magnitude, meaning that the magnitudes derived using probabilistic cataloging can only be validated to the tenth of a magnitude level of precision. Furthermore, color corrections proved to be too difficult in this region. Consequently, in Section 11.2 of the Appendix, I provide independent validation of probabilistic cataloging photometry by comparing probabilistic cataloging to `Photo` when run on a sparse field.

³⁶ <http://classic.sdss.org/legacy/>

³⁷ Because star-galaxy differentiation is a complicated topic in its own right, this has been postponed for future work.

I have thus established test conditions under which the performances of probabilistic cataloging and DAOPHOT can be quantified and compared. I will hereafter refer to the [An et al. \(2008\)](#) catalog as the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog and the [Sarajedini et al. \(2007\)](#) HST ACS F606W-band catalog as the HST catalog for shorthand.

6. RESULTS I: THE CATALOG ENSEMBLE

In this chapter, I define catalog performance metrics and demonstrate that probabilistic cataloging accurately probes over a magnitude deeper in the test field than does DAOPHOT, the best-performing of the traditional cataloging algorithms in the crowded limit (Becker et al. 2007). In particular, using the test conditions described in Chapter 5, I quantify and compare the performances of the two cataloging algorithms by comparing the catalog ensemble to the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog via the HST catalog, which I adopt as a proxy for the true stellar population. All tests of this implementation of probabilistic cataloging were run on `fink1`, a machine with two six-core Intel Xeon E5-2667 processors at 2.9 GHz. Unless explicitly stated otherwise, all presented results are derived from a run with $f_{min} = 250$ and a penalty of $3/2$ in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source. On `fink1`, this run required approximately one day of wall clock time. The catalog ensemble was created by taking 300 random draws from the posterior, where each sample was given a weight in the draw according to its posterior weight, which was described in Section 4.6.

6.1. *Depicting the Catalog Ensemble*

Before proceeding with results related to the catalog ensemble, it is instructive to familiarize the reader with the graphical representation of the catalog ensemble that will be adopted throughout this thesis. Indeed, because the catalog ensemble is a collection of many catalogs, it is important that its graphical representation is clear, especially in regard to differentiating between the ensemble itself and a single catalog sample from the ensemble.

In Figure 2, I present a six panel plot of five random catalog samples and the full stacked catalog ensemble of 300 catalog samples plotted over a subregion of the observed image. The five panels labeled “Sample i ”, $1 \leq i \leq 5$, each display a single catalog sample from the catalog ensemble, whereas the sixth panel in the bottom-right corner labeled “Stacked Ensemble” displays the catalog ensemble itself. In all of these panels, the area of each marker scales with the flux of the inferred source that it represents.

One primary feature of the catalog ensemble is that an inferred source's significance correlates with the fraction of samples in which it appears, and a source's uncertainties in position and flux can be derived directly from the respective distributions across the catalog ensemble.³⁸ Both of these phenomena can be observed in the graphical representations of the catalog samples. For example, in scanning among the five catalog samples that have been plotted, one can see that the bright source located at (74, 61.5) appears in every sample with well-constrained position and flux, as evidenced by the fact that positions and sizes of the markers are stable across all five of the samples. Contrastingly, the faint source located at (71.5, 56.5) appears only in sample 4, an indication of the marginal significance of that source.

Of course, identifying uncertain sources by scanning through individual catalog samples is both tedious and challenging. Consequently, I introduce the stacked catalog ensemble. In the stacked catalog ensemble, all 300 samples from the catalog ensemble have been plotted over the subregion of the SDSS observed image. The opacity of each marker is set to 1% in order to allow overlapping sources from different catalog samples to be identifiable by eye. Plotting the stacked catalog ensemble in this manner has a distinct advantage over plotting the catalog samples individually: it enables the position and flux distributions of an individual source, as well as a source's covariances with its neighbors, to be identified easily upon inspection in a single plot. The most pertinent information in the individual catalog samples is encoded in the stacked catalog ensemble, and furthermore, one does not have to flip between samples to infer whether a source is well-constrained. For example, in examining the stacked catalog ensemble plot, it is clear that the source at (74, 61.5) is well-constrained in both position and flux, while the source at (71.5, 56.5) is not. For these reasons, this graphical representation of the stacked catalog ensemble will be adopted throughout the rest of this thesis.

³⁸ This is described at length in Chapter 7.

Figure 2. A six panel plot displaying a 10×10 pixel subregion of the SDSS r -band test image. In each of the five plots labeled “Sample i ,” $1 \leq i \leq 5$, a random catalog sample from the catalog ensemble has been plotted over the subregion. The colorbar values are in units of ADU. The area of each red x marker scales with the flux of the inferred source in the catalog. In the sixth plot labeled ‘Stacked Ensemble,’ all 300 samples from the catalog ensemble have been plotted over the subregion. In this plot, the opacity of each marker is 1%.

6.2. *Quantifying Performance: Completeness & False Discovery Rate*

I begin the presentation of new results by introducing tests used to quantify catalog performance. In particular, by treating the HST catalog as ground truth, I define two metrics for assessing the performance of the catalog ensemble and the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog: completeness and false discovery rate.

Perhaps the most canonical metric of catalog performance is completeness: the fraction of true sources at a given apparent magnitude that are contained in a catalog. Treating the HST catalog as ground truth, I define catalog completeness in this instance as the fraction of sources in the HST catalog within a given magnitude range that have corresponding sources in the catalog of interest. Given that the catalog ensemble is a collection of catalogs, as opposed to just one catalog, the completeness of the catalog ensemble within a magnitude bin is taken to be the average of such completeness values over all catalog samples in the ensemble.

While completeness is an important metric, it cannot be used as the only metric of assessing catalog performance, as it does not incorporate a notion of false detections. Indeed, it is possible to construct a catalog of no physical significance that nonetheless has a completeness of 100%: one could simply place sources at all locations with all possible fluxes. In order to quantify such effects, I introduce the false discovery rate metric. Here, I define a true positive (TP) as a source in the catalog of interest within a given magnitude range that has a match in the HST catalog. A false positive (FP) is a source without such a match. Accordingly, I define the false discovery rate (FDR) as the fraction of total sources in the catalog of interest that are false positives in the given magnitude bin:

$$FDR = \frac{FP}{TP+FP} \quad (37)$$

Analogous to the calculation of completeness for the catalog ensemble, the false discovery rate in a magnitude bin is defined to be the average of such false discovery rates over all samples in the catalog ensemble.

Of course, I must specify how a match is determined in this context. An HST source is said to have a corresponding source, or match, in the catalog of interest if there is a source in the catalog of interest with a position within 0.75 pixels of the HST source position and an SDSS r -magnitude within 0.5 magnitudes of the HST F606W magnitude.³⁹ The magnitude constraint suppresses the probability of random matches and prevents severely oversplit sources⁴⁰ from being counted toward completeness. Furthermore, it accounts for magnitude discrepancies caused by the different filters used by the two surveys. The 0.75 pixel match radius accounts for limitations in cross-matching positions, such as each survey’s position measurement uncertainty and inconsistencies due to the proper motions of the observed stars between observations. Although the 0.75 pixel and 0.5 magnitude match radii may seem overly generous, the high degree of crowding in the field naturally leads to more confusion in the catalogs, and the main intent of the matching algorithm is to enforce 0 completeness in the faint limit by preventing random matches. Nonetheless, I experiment with a wide range of match criteria later in this section in order to demonstrate that the results are robust to different match radii.

In Figure 3, I present a plot of completeness as a function of HST F606W magnitude for the catalog ensemble and for the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog. From this plot, it is evident that the catalog ensemble has a higher completeness than the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog in every magnitude bin. Of interest is the integrated area between the two curves: because the flux distribution follows a power law, the gain in completeness at 21st and 22nd magnitudes corresponds to the detection of many hundreds of additional stars by the catalog ensemble. Significantly, the catalog ensemble probes *over a magnitude deeper* in completeness.

In Figure 4, I present a plot of the false discovery rate as a function of SDSS r magnitude for the catalog ensemble and for the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog. While both catalogs maintain false discovery rates of 0 up to 17th magnitude, the catalog ensemble has a significantly lower false discovery rate between 17th and 20th magnitudes. The relatively high

³⁹ Sources located in the outer 2.5 pixel border of the image are removed from the matching algorithm in order to account for edge effects.

⁴⁰ An oversplit source is a single true source that has been “split” into multiple sources in a catalog. This is often a consequence of a PSF mismatch.

false discovery rate of the catalog ensemble beyond 20th magnitude is *not* an indication of the catalog ensemble performing poorly but rather a consequence of the DAOPHOT catalog’s poor completeness beyond 20th magnitude. Many of the catalog ensemble’s false positives in this regime correspond to a situation in which multiple faint, neighboring HST stars are entirely undetected by DAOPHOT but are cataloged as one source by probabilistic cataloging, where the magnitude of the identified source is more than 0.5 magnitudes less than those of any of the HST stars.^{41,42}

In order to verify this phenomenon, I present Figures 5 and 6, which compare the completeness and false discovery rate of the catalog ensemble to those of the DAOPHOT catalog as the position and magnitude match radii are varied. In Figure 5, one can see that the false discovery rate of the catalog ensemble at 21st magnitude approaches that of the DAOPHOT catalog as the magnitude match radius is increased, indicating that blending is indeed the cause of the high false discovery rate of the catalog ensemble in the faint limit. Perhaps more significantly, the plots in Figures 5 and 6 reveal that the catalog ensemble maintains a completeness of over one magnitude deeper, as well as a lower false discovery rate up to 20th magnitude, *even as the match radii are varied*.

6.3. Residuals

In addition to the previously defined metrics, it is beneficial to consider example subregions of the image showing various degrees of crowding. In Figures 7, 8, 9, and 10, I present four subregions comparing the catalog ensemble to the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog. These four subregions were selected to be a fair representation of the spectrum of crowding in the full 100×100 pixel image.

In Figure 7, analysis of the residuals in the rightmost column reveals that the mean model image generated with the catalog ensemble reproduces the observed image to a higher degree of fidelity than does the model image generated with the DAOPHOT catalog. Fur-

⁴¹ I present concrete examples illustrating this phenomenon in the twelve-panel plots in the next section, Section 6.3.

⁴² Another potential cause of the high false discovery rate could be f_{min} . As described in Section 11.1 in the Appendix, for sources with true fluxes below f_{min} , the chain assigns the sources fluxes equal to f_{min} , which could inadvertently cause the assigned fluxes of the sources to fluctuate high by over half a magnitude, even if the positions are correctly identified.

Figure 3. A plot comparing the completeness of the catalog ensemble to the completeness of the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog.

Figure 4. A plot comparing the false discovery rate of the catalog ensemble to the false discovery rate of the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog.

Figure 5. A ten-panel plot comparing the completeness and false discovery rate of the catalog ensemble in red to those of the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog in blue for five magnitude bins, where the magnitude match radius is varied from 0.25 to 1. The position match radius is held fixed at 0.75 pixels.

Figure 6. A ten-panel plot comparing the completeness and false discovery rate of the catalog ensemble in red to those of the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog in blue for five magnitude bins, where the position match radius is varied from 0.25 pixels to 1.25 pixels. The magnitude match radius is held fixed at 0.5 magnitudes.

thermore, in the 2D plots of the subregions, one can find by eye numerous cases in which the catalog ensemble identifies HST sources that are missed by the DAOPHOT catalog. For example, in Figure 7, the HST catalog identifies five stars brighter than 22nd magnitude located in the region (74-78, 57-60). The catalog ensemble identifies all five of these HST sources, whereas the DAOPHOT catalog combines the five HST sources into two sources. In addition, the HST source located at (77.5, 62) is detected by the catalog ensemble but not by the DAOPHOT catalog.

These same phenomena found in Figure 7 can be found in Figures 8, 9, and 10. In particular, all of these subregions contain cases in which the catalog ensemble identifies more HST sources than does the DAOPHOT catalog. In each of these cases, the DAOPHOT catalog either fails to identify a source or places one or two sources at the “center of mass” of the HST sources in question. Furthermore, in all of these subregions, the residuals of the mean catalog ensemble model image are significantly smaller than those of the DAOPHOT catalog model image, further indicating that the catalog ensemble more accurately retains the information in the test image.

Figure 7. Plots of the residuals for the same 10×10 pixel subregion of the image shown in Figure 2. The pixel values are all in units of ADU. The **red x** markers with opacity values of 1% correspond to sources from the stacked catalog ensemble, **blue +** markers correspond to sources from the DAOPHOT catalog, **lime green +** markers correspond to HST sources brighter than 22nd magnitude, and **forest green +** markers correspond to HST sources between 22nd and 25th magnitudes. The area of each marker scales with the underlying source flux. Furthermore, the sizes of the ‘+’ markers are scaled with the sizes of the ‘x’ markers such that if a ‘+’ marker and an ‘x’ marker enclose the same area, then they represent sources of the same flux. The SDSS DAOPHOT model image refers to the model image generated using the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog and the PSF produced by the SDSS pipeline. The mean PCAT image refers to the mean of the model images generated using the samples from the catalog ensemble and the same PSF produced by the SDSS pipeline. The spread of the residual values of the SDSS DAOPHOT model image is significantly greater than the spread of the residual values of the PCAT model image. *This figure is 300 DPI and should support high magnification using any PDF viewer.*

Figure 8. An analogous figure to Figure 7 for a different subregion of the image. The pixel values are all in units of ADU.

Figure 9. An analogous figure to Figure 7 for a different subregion of the image. The pixel values are all in units of ADU.

Figure 10. An analogous figure to Figure 7 for a different subregion of the image. The pixel values are all in units of ADU.

7. CONDENSED CATALOG

Despite the benefits of the catalog ensemble, one could argue that the catalog ensemble complicates the canonical framework for astrophysical research: it is computationally more expensive to retain an entire ensemble than just one catalog, and many tools in astrophysical research are designed specifically for the input of a *single* catalog. Furthermore, the most statistically significant sources in a catalog ensemble are by nature present in all of the catalog samples, even in the crowded limit. Thus, the question is raised as to whether the information preserved in the catalog ensemble can be distilled down to a single catalog with minimal information loss for these sources.

In this section, I provide a procedure for the distillation of a catalog ensemble into a single catalog, which I call the “condensed catalog.” Significantly, because the condensed catalog is derived from the catalog ensemble, *the condensed catalog retains a fully marginalized posterior including full covariances and uncertainties*, a desirable feature not possessed by traditional catalogs. Furthermore, I introduce an additional condensed catalog parameter called “sigfac,” which quantifies the degree to which a source has been affected by crowding, thus providing a method for identifying spurious sources.

7.1. Labeling Procedure

As described in Section 3.6, for a catalog with N sources, the catalog space is $N!$ degenerate, and the prior and likelihood are invariant to the labeling of sources (Portillo et al. 2017). Thus, the ordering of the sources in the catalog samples within the catalog ensemble cannot be treated as a consistent labeling across the ensemble. Naturally, the distillation of the catalog ensemble into a condensed catalog requires some form of labeling in order to recover position and flux distributions, and consequently, I must present a procedure for labeling. As long as this labeling procedure can consistently label the most prevalent sources present across the samples in the ensemble, the condensed catalog will retain information about the most significant sources. It is of less consequence if the labeling procedure does not recover the less prevalent, faint, and blended sources as accurately because the catalog ensemble is naturally more uncertain about these sources. However, as will be shown

later in this chapter, many such sources are recovered and accordingly assigned high sigfac values.

The labeling procedure that I propose is in spirit a clustering algorithm, as the question of labeling can be thought of alternatively as a question of clustering in 3-dimensional space over x, y , and flux: the closer that two catalog points from different catalog samples are to one another in x, y , flux space, the more likely they are to represent the same source. However, clustering algorithms such as k -means clustering suffer from the complication of having to define a metric with an appropriate weighting of distance in position (x, y) space relative to distance in flux space.⁴³ To circumvent this, I propose a labeling procedure based on sorting the fluxes from brightest to faintest and then iteratively matching points in 2-dimensional position space according to this method:

1. A “seed” catalog is created according to the following procedure. The catalog ensemble is first stacked. All neighbors across the stacked ensemble are then identified, where source B is a neighbor of source A if source B belongs to a different catalog sample and is the closest source within a 0.75 pixel radius of source A among the catalog sample, if such a source exists. The source with the most neighbors across the stacked ensemble is then found and identified as a seed. This source and its neighbors are then removed from the stacked ensemble, where the neighbor counts of affected sources are decremented appropriately. This process is repeated until every source has been associated with a seed. Each seed is then added to the seed catalog, along with an associated value that I call *prevalence*: the fraction of samples in the catalog ensemble containing a source associated with the given seed. A modest cut of 10% on prevalence is then imposed to eliminate spurious sources.
2. Next, the seed catalog is sorted in decreasing order of flux. Beginning with the brightest source in the seed catalog, the catalog samples are then iterated over in order to identify the brightest source within a radius of 0.75 pixels in each catalog sample,

⁴³ Kiefer Hicks (a former member of Professor Finkbeiner’s group) and I experimented with the application of various popular clustering algorithms in October, 2016, but none of these clustering algorithms performed adequately.

if such a source exists. Once all samples in the catalog ensemble have been considered, the points matched to the brightest source in the seed catalog are collectively defined as a cluster. These points are subsequently removed from the algorithm, and the procedure is repeated for the next-brightest source in the seed catalog, etc., until all sources in the seed catalog have been considered. Each cluster is then distilled down to a single source with:

- mean x , y , and flux values
- x , y , and flux uncertainties
- the prevalence value defined in step 1
- position and flux sigfac values introduced in Section 7.2

The use of the seed catalog, as opposed to an arbitrary catalog sample as a seed in step 2, is motivated by the fact that many prevalent sources have a prevalence of 98-99% (a high prevalence but nonetheless not 100%). Thus, an unfortunate choice of an arbitrary catalog sample as a seed could result in selecting a catalog sample among the 1-2% in which the source is not identified. Because the labeling procedure requires a source in the initial seed catalog in order to identify a cluster, it would not be possible for that source to be present in the resulting condensed catalog, even though the source is statistically significant. By creating a seed catalog according to the aforementioned labeling procedure, the condensed catalog does not suffer from such potential incompleteness.

Another benefit of this labeling procedure is that it contains only two parameters: the prevalence cut on the condensed catalog (chosen here to be 10%) and the match radius (chosen here to be 0.75 pixels). The prevalence cut serves to eliminate spurious clusters. As seen in Figure 11, the overwhelming majority of sources in the seed catalog have a prevalence less than 10% or greater than 95%. The primary cause of the sources with prevalences less than 10% is the requirement in the labeling procedure that every source in the catalog ensemble be placed into a cluster. For example, 239 sources in the seed catalog represent clusters with exactly 1 member, and 145 sources represent clusters with 2 mem-

bers. Naturally, sources with such low prevalences are spurious and should be eliminated from the seed catalog. Because a much stricter prevalence cut on the resulting catalog would almost certainly be adopted in any real scientific application in order to eliminate spurious sources, the exact value of this prevalence cut around 10% on the seed catalog is ultimately of little consequence.

The match radius of 0.75 pixels was chosen empirically. In Figures 12, 13, 14, and 15, I present examples demonstrating the efficacy of the labeling procedure with this match radius applied to the catalog ensemble analyzed in Chapter 6. The four regions presented in these figures are the same four regions presented in the twelve-panel plots from Section 6.3. By-eye analysis of these figures reveals that the labeling procedure performs well with the chosen 0.75 pixel match radius, as the labeling procedure both captures the overwhelming majority of sources in the stacked catalog ensemble and resolves the individual clusters. Indeed, I empirically tested different match radii and determined 0.75 pixels to be the optimal value: match radii stricter than 0.75 pixels result in sources being omitted from their proper clusters, and match radii more generous than 0.75 pixels result in distinct clusters being merged. Furthermore, 0.75 pixels is also the match radius used in calculating completeness and false discovery rate in Section 6.2 and in this regard is consistent.

7.2. *Quantifying Crowding: Sigma Factor (sigfac)*

It is beneficial to define a parameter in the condensed catalog that quantifies the degree to which a source is spurious or contaminated by its neighbors. This can be achieved by determining the factor by which the uncertainties in position and flux of a source as reported in the condensed catalog exceed the expected uncertainties of an isolated source with the same flux in a sparse field. I define this value for position and flux to be the sigma factor, which I abbreviate as sigfac. Naturally, sources that are heavily contaminated by neighbors, sources that are not appropriately deblended, and sources that are not fit well due to a PSF mismatch will have higher sigfac values. Consequently, these undesirable sources could be eliminated by imposing a sigfac cut.

Figure 11. Histograms showing the prevalence distributions of sources within the seed catalog and the condensed catalog. The left plots show the distributions of prevalence, and the right plots show the distributions of the number of samples with a source in a given cluster (here, this is equal to the prevalence multiplied by 300). The condensed catalog histograms do not have large concentrations of sources with low prevalence due to the 10% prevalence cut imposed on the seed catalog.

Figure 12. A two-panel plot showing the results of the clustering algorithm on a 10×10 pixel subregion of the image, using a 0.75 pixel match radius and a prevalence cut of 10%. The left panel shows the stacked catalog ensemble plotted over the SDSS observed image, where the area of each ‘x’ marker scales with the flux of the source that it represents. The pixel values in the left plot are in units of ADU. The right panel shows the clusters, as identified by the labeling procedure. All points with the same color belong to the same cluster. The black ‘+’ markers correspond to points that do not belong to a cluster (consequences of the modest prevalence cut on the seed catalog). The sizes of the ‘+’ markers are scaled with the sizes of the ‘x’ markers such that if a ‘+’ marker and an ‘x’ marker enclose the same area, then they represent sources of the same flux. Although each ‘x’ marker has an opacity value of 5%, each ‘+’ marker has an opacity of 100% so that all sources not belonging to a cluster can easily be identified by eye. *This figure is 300 DPI and should support high magnification using any PDF viewer.*

Figure 13. A two-panel plot showing the results of the clustering algorithm on another subregion of the image. The clustering algorithm performs well on this subregion.

Figure 14. A two-panel plot showing the results of the clustering algorithm on another subregion of the image. The clustering algorithm performs well on this subregion.

Figure 15. A two-panel plot showing the results of the clustering algorithm on another subregion of the image. This subregion is the most crowded of four example subregions. Consequently, the clustering algorithm performs worst on this subregion among the four. However, relatively isolated sources are still clustered appropriately, and the cases in which the clustering algorithm is confused are indeed ambiguous regions: it is not clear how one should label the catalog ensemble at those locations.

In order to calculate sigfac values, it is necessary to derive the theoretical uncertainty in position and flux of an isolated source with a given flux in a sparse field. Indeed, I provide derivations in Sections 11.4 and 11.5 of the Appendix. To confirm empirically that these derived uncertainties are correct, I present Figure 16, which shows the fractional flux errors and position errors of sources from the condensed catalog as functions of SDSS r -magnitude.⁴⁴ The red curves correspond to multiples ($1\times$, $2\times$, $4\times$, and $8\times$) of the expected errors of sources if they were isolated in a sparse field for a range of magnitudes. The $1\times$ curve for the fractional flux error was calculated using equation (54), with an additional floor of 1% added to account for effects such as the PSF mismatch. Similarly, the $1\times$ curve for the position error was calculated using equation (71), with an additional floor of 0.005 pixels added. This figure demonstrates that the derivations in Section 11.4 and 11.5 of the Appendix accurately predict the floors on fractional flux and position errors: the $1\times$ expected curves are in excellent agreement with the lower bounds on the points in the scatter plots. Thus, the flux and position sigfac parameters are meaningful indicators of the additional uncertainty caused by crowding.

⁴⁴ This figure was made by Stephen Portillo.

Figure 16. Plots of fractional flux error and position error as functions of SDSS r -magnitude. The fractional flux error of a source is calculated as the reported flux uncertainty in the condensed catalog divided by the flux of the source. The $1\times$, $2\times$, $4\times$, and $8\times$ expected curves refer to the expected errors if each source were isolated in a sparse field. These plots were made by Stephen Portillo.

8. RESULTS II: THE CONDENSED CATALOG

In this chapter, I demonstrate that the condensed catalog performs almost identically to the catalog ensemble on the 100×100 pixel test image according to the metrics of completeness and false discovery rate defined in Chapter 6. Furthermore, I demonstrate the effectiveness of sigfac as a tuning parameter for the condensed catalog. All of the results presented in this chapter are derived from the same run that was presented in Chapter 6, which had $f_{\min} = 250$ and a penalty of $3/2$ in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source. The condensed catalog was created using the catalog ensemble from this run according to the labeling procedure described in Section 7.1.

8.1. *Completeness & False Discovery Rate*

In Figure 17, I present a plot of the completeness values of the condensed catalog, the catalog ensemble, and the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog as functions of HST F606W magnitude. The completeness of the condensed catalog was calculated using the same procedure outlined in Section 6.2, except that each matched source was given a weight equal to its prevalence. Significantly, the completeness of the condensed catalog is almost identical to that of the catalog ensemble. The fact that the condensed catalog slightly outperforms the catalog ensemble in some magnitude bins is entirely an artifact of the matching algorithm.⁴⁵

In Figure 18, I present a plot of the false discovery rates of the condensed catalog, the catalog ensemble, and the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog as functions of SDSS r -magnitude. The false discovery rate of the condensed catalog was calculated using the same procedure as in Section 6.2, with the following modification: if a source with prevalence p in the condensed catalog had a match in the HST catalog, the source contributed p fraction of a true positive, and if it did not have a match, it contributed p fraction of a false positive. Just

⁴⁵ This is demonstrated by the following example. Consider an HST-matched source in the condensed catalog with a large spread in position across the catalog ensemble, such that not all of the corresponding sources contributing to prevalence lie within the 0.75 pixel match radius. In condensing the catalog ensemble via the labeling procedure, *all* corresponding sources in the ensemble contributing to prevalence are collapsed onto the source in the condensed catalog, which lies inside of the match radius. Thus, in this case, sources that do not contribute to the completeness of the catalog ensemble do contribute to the completeness of the condensed catalog via prevalence. Nonetheless, this effect should be negligible for a source with high prevalence, and the fact that the completeness of the condensed catalog is almost identical to that of the catalog ensemble indicates that the labeling procedure retains most of the valuable information about high prevalence sources contained in the catalog ensemble.

as with completeness, the false discovery rate of the condensed catalog follows that of the catalog ensemble.

In order to confirm that the performance of the condensed catalog is not a consequence of the specific choices of position and magnitude match radii, I present Figures 19 and 20, which compare the completeness and false discovery rates of the condensed catalog, catalog ensemble, and DAOPHOT catalog as the magnitude and position match radii are varied. Both figures indicate that the completeness and the false discovery rate of the condensed catalog are almost identical to those of the catalog ensemble, irrespective of the choices of position and flux match radii. Thus, the labeling procedure for distilling the catalog ensemble into the condensed catalog is performing as desired: the labeling procedure results in minimal information loss for high prevalence sources, and the condensed catalog retains the primary benefits of the catalog ensemble while also being simpler to use and conceptualize.

8.2. Cuts on *Sigfac*

As described in Section 7.2, the principle reason for including the flux and position *sigfac* parameters in the condensed catalog is that cuts on *sigfac* provide a method for eliminating spurious sources. Accordingly, in this section, I explore the effects of *sigfac* cuts. Significantly, the flux and position *sigfac* parameters can also be calculated for the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog, as the DAOPHOT catalog contains position and flux uncertainties, and the expected sparse field uncertainties are derived in Sections 11.4 and 11.5 in the Appendix.⁴⁶ Thus, it is possible to test the effects of *sigfac* cuts on completeness and false discovery rate for both the condensed catalog and the DAOPHOT catalog. However, because the uncertainties in the DAOPHOT catalog are *not* fully marginalized, the *sigfac* values for the sources in the DAOPHOT catalog are underestimates in comparison to the *sigfac* values for sources in the condensed catalog.

⁴⁶ These expected uncertainties have the noise floors added to them, as described in Section 7.2.

Figure 17. An analogous plot to Figure 3 comparing the completeness of the condensed catalog to that of the catalog ensemble and of the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog.

Figure 18. An analogous plot to Figure 4 comparing the false discovery rate of the condensed catalog to that of the catalog ensemble and of the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog.

Figure 19. An analogous ten-panel plot to Figure 5 comparing the completeness and false discovery rate of the condensed catalog in purple to those of the catalog ensemble in red and of the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog in blue for five magnitude bins, where the magnitude match radius is varied from 0.25 to 1. The position match radius is held fixed at 0.75 pixels.

Figure 20. An analogous ten-panel plot to Figure 6 comparing the completeness and false discovery rate of the condensed catalog in purple to those of the catalog ensemble in red and of the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog in blue for five magnitude bins, where the position match radius is varied from 0.25 pixels to 1.25 pixels. The magnitude match radius is held fixed at 0.5 magnitudes.

In Figure 21, I present the completeness values of the condensed catalog and the DAOPHOT catalog before and after a flux sigfac cut of 8. The condensed catalog's completeness decreases only slightly as a result of the flux sigfac cut, and the DAOPHOT catalog's completeness remains virtually unchanged. However, as just mentioned, the DAOPHOT catalog's uncertainty estimates are underestimates, and consequently, a sigfac cut of 8 removes a higher fraction of sources in the condensed catalog than in the DAOPHOT catalog. Regardless, the condensed catalog's completeness after the cut is still substantially higher than the DAOPHOT catalog's completeness *before* the cut.

In Figure 22, I present the false discovery rates of the condensed catalog and the DAOPHOT catalog before and after a flux sigfac cut of 8. The false discovery rates of both the condensed catalog and the DAOPHOT catalog drop with the cut, but the condensed catalog's false discovery rate improves more substantially. Significantly, with this sigfac cut, the condensed catalog maintains a false discovery rate of 10% or lower until 20th magnitude. This suggests that the flux sigfac parameter captures to first order the extent to which a source is spurious.

As seen in Figures 21 and 22, a cut on sigfac is a trade-off between completeness and false discovery rate. Spurious sources with high sigfac values are more likely to be false positives and thus are more likely to decrease the false discovery rate when removed with a sigfac cut. However, by eliminating these spurious sources, completeness is inevitably lowered. In order to explore this trade-off, I have included Figure 23, a receiver operating characteristic curve that displays curves in false discovery rate-completeness space.⁴⁷ The curves are formed by varying the discrimination threshold, which in this instance is the sigfac cut. In this plot, a value closer to the upper-left corner is indicative of a better catalog. Each curve represents a different magnitude bin of the condensed catalog or the DAOPHOT catalog.

Figure 23 confirms the observations made about Figures 21 and 22 for a wide range of sigfac cuts ranging from 1 to 32. For each magnitude bin, the entire curve in false discovery

⁴⁷ This plot was made by Stephen Portillo.

rate-completeness space for the condensed catalog lies as close or closer to the upper-left corner than does the curve for the DAOPHOT catalog, indicating that for most sigfac cuts between 1 and 32, the condensed catalog has both a higher completeness and a lower false discovery rate than does the DAOPHOT catalog. Of particular interest is that the condensed catalog at magnitude 19 performs similarly to the DAOPHOT catalog at magnitude 18, and the condensed catalog at magnitude 20 definitively outperforms the DAOPHOT catalog at magnitude 19. This provides even stronger evidence that the catalog ensemble outperforms the DAOPHOT catalog by over one magnitude according to these metrics.

Figure 21. A plot comparing the completeness values of the condensed catalog and the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog before and after a sigfac cut of 8. The DAOPHOT curves before and after the sigfac cut directly coincide.

Figure 22. A plot comparing the false discovery rates of the condensed catalog and the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog before and after a sigfac cut of 8.

Figure 23. A receiver operating characteristic curve that displays curves in false discovery rate - completeness space obtained by varying the sigfac cut from 1 to 32. Here, curves are plotted for four magnitude bins for both the condensed catalog and the DAOPHOT catalog. The magnitude bins are each one magnitude wide and centered on the magnitude listed in the legend (e.g., mag 18 refers to a magnitude bin extending from mag 17.5 to mag 18.5). Because a completeness of 100% and a false discovery rate of 0% are desired, a better catalog is characterized by a curve closer to the upper-left corner of the plot. This plot was made by Stephen Portillo.

9. RESULTS III: RESPONSE TO DIFFERENT SEEING CONDITIONS

In this chapter, I demonstrate probabilistic cataloging’s robustness to different seeing conditions. As described in Section 5.3, a primary advantage of M2 as a test field is that M2 lies on Stripe 82, a 300 deg² stripe on the Celestial Equator that has been repeatedly imaged by SDSS in the *ugriz* bands (Jiang 2014). In particular, SDSS has taken 13 *r*-band exposures of the exact test region adopted for analysis throughout this thesis. These exposures are subject to different seeing conditions, ranging from 1.04'' seeing to 1.92'' seeing. They are pertinent to this thesis because they provide yet another method of assessing probabilistic cataloging’s performance: measuring probabilistic cataloging’s response to information loss in the form of worse seeing. Furthermore, these exposures can be used to quantify the maximum seeing for which probabilistic cataloging recovers similar completeness and false discovery rate values as does DAOPHOT when run on the original 1.05'' seeing exposure.

9.1. Data Reduction of Exposures

I will first briefly describe the data reduction process for these exposures. Detailed information on the 13 exposures, including their identification numbers in the SDSS Data Release 12 pipeline and their seeing values, is enumerated in Table 1. I prepared these exposures for probabilistic cataloging according to the following procedure. First, using the `astropy.wcs.wcs_pix2world` and `wcs_world2pix` functions, I mapped the coordinates (640–740, 700–800) of the 100 × 100 pixel region in the 1.05'' seeing image (run 2583, field 2, camcol 136 in the SDSS Data Release 12 Pipeline) to the corresponding pixel coordinates $(x'_1 - x'_2, y'_1 - y'_2)$ for each of the other exposures. I then floored these coordinates to $(\lfloor x'_1 \rfloor - \lfloor x'_2 \rfloor, \lfloor y'_1 \rfloor - \lfloor y'_2 \rfloor)$ in order to obtain coordinates that could then be extracted from the appropriate idR file. For each of the exposures, I then extracted this 100 × 100 pixel region and the SDSS pipeline-generated PSF, as well as the gain, bias, and counts-to-nanomaggies conversion, according to the procedure described at the end of Section 5.2.

Table 1. A table detailing 13 different exposures of the test field.

Run	Field	Camcol	Seeing (")
1040	2	155	1.52326
1755	2	132	1.17485
2583	2	136	1.04759
3360	2	116	1.34784
3388	2	75	1.77287
3427	2	103	1.76634
3434	2	108	1.61779
4187	2	105	1.04490
4192	2	111	1.13964
4203	2	160	1.91528
4822	5	198	1.39768
4930	2	147	1.91363
7778	6	72	1.37098

Due to WCS transformation distortions, 4 exposures had to be discarded: runs 1755, 3427, 4822, and 7778. Consequently, I processed 9 runs in full. In Figure 24, I present a nine-panel plot of the same 10×10 pixel subregion extracted from each of the nine exposures in order to demonstrate the effect that seeing has on the field. This subregion is the same subregion shown in Figures 7 and 12.

All runs presented in the following section were processed on `fink1` (a machine with two six-core Intel Xeon E5-2667 processors at 2.9 GHz), `fink2` (a machine with 2 twelve-core Intel Xeon E5-2760 v3 processors at 2.3 GHz), and the ITC cluster (a cluster with 16 nodes, each with 2 Intel 18-core E5-2699v3 Haswell processors with 7.1 GB of RAM per core).

9.2. *Completeness, False Discovery Rate, and Beyond*

I begin the presentation of these results by quantifying probabilistic cataloging’s response to different seeing conditions using the metrics of completeness and false discovery rate introduced in Section 6.2.⁴⁸ In Figure 25, I present a plot of the completeness of the catalog ensemble for a range of seeing conditions, as well as the completeness of the SDSS

⁴⁸ The matching algorithm used to compute completeness and false discovery rate in this chapter is the same matching algorithm described in Section 6.2.

Figure 24. A nine-panel plot showing the same 10×10 pixel region for nine exposures with different seeing. All nine panels have the same colorbar stretch. The pixel values are all in units of ADU. Due to the WCS transformations described in the data reduction procedure outlined in Section 9.1, the actual pixels in each exposure are misaligned at a sub-pixel level. In order to adjust for these sub-pixel shifts, the above regions have been interpolated onto the correct coordinates using 2D cubic interpolation.

DAOPHOT catalog derived from the 1.05'' seeing exposure for comparison.⁴⁹ As expected, the catalog ensemble's completeness decreases as a function of seeing. Of particular significance is that the catalog ensemble derived from the 1.62'' seeing exposure maintains a similar completeness to that of the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog derived from the 1.05'' seeing exposure.

In Figure 26, I present a plot of the false discovery rate of the catalog ensemble for a range of seeing conditions, as well as the false discovery rate of the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog derived from the 1.05'' seeing exposure. As expected, the false discovery rate of the catalog ensemble increases as a function of seeing. Significantly, up to 19th magnitude, the catalog ensemble derived from the 1.35'' seeing exposure maintains a similar false discovery rate to that of the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog derived from the 1.05'' seeing exposure. This, in conjunction with the fact that the catalog ensemble derived from the 1.35'' seeing exposure has a completeness of over half a magnitude greater than that of the DAOPHOT catalog, indicates that probabilistic cataloging is robust to different seeing conditions.

In order to explore further the relationship between completeness and seeing, I present Figure 27, a plot of completeness as a function of seeing for a range of magnitudes. This plot is an alternative representation of the information in Figure 25 above 18th magnitude. As expected, the faintest HST sources are identified in none of the exposures.

Lastly, I present Figures 28, 29, 30, and 31, which depict the catalog ensembles derived from the different exposures. The four selected subregions are the same example subregions analyzed in Sections 6.3 and 7.1. In these four figures, the degradation of the catalog ensemble as a function of seeing is immediately apparent. The primary manifestation of this degradation is that sources are deblended with less frequency as seeing increases. For example, in Figure 28, the 5 HST sources brighter than 22nd magnitude in the region (74-78, 57-60) incrementally blend together as seeing increases. Such examples are present in all four figures.

⁴⁹ This 1.05'' exposure corresponds to the exposure used for analysis throughout the other chapters of this thesis.

Nonetheless, the catalog ensembles derived from the exposures with higher seeing values are impressive in their own right. For example, in the subregion depicted in Figure 31, the catalog ensemble derived from the 1.62'' seeing exposure is more complete than the DAOPHOT catalog derived from the 1.05'' seeing exposure. Interestingly, in Figure 29, the catalog ensemble derived from the 1.62'' seeing exposure blends the four HST sources brighter than 22nd magnitude in the region (66.5-71, 36.5-38.5) into two sources in exactly the same manner as does the DAOPHOT catalog. This phenomenon is present in multiple instances, suggesting that the failure modes of probabilistic cataloging are similar to those of DAOPHOT, except that probabilistic cataloging is less sensitive to information loss.

Figure 25. A plot comparing the completeness of the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog at $1.05''$ seeing to the completeness of the catalog ensemble for a wide range of seeing conditions. The dashed line corresponds to the completeness of the catalog ensemble derived from the $1.91''$ seeing exposure. The 0 completeness of this catalog ensemble for the brightest stars is due to oversplitting, as evidenced by the bright star at position (23.5, 48.5) in Figure 31. In this plot, I have omitted the $1.04''$ seeing and $1.92''$ seeing exposures due to the redundancy of these exposures with the $1.05''$ seeing and $1.91''$ seeing exposures, respectively. Furthermore, I have omitted the $1.14''$ seeing exposure in order to keep the plot uncluttered.

Figure 26. A plot comparing the false discovery rate of the SDSS DAOPHOT catalog at $1.05''$ seeing to the false discovery rate of the catalog ensemble for a wide range of seeing conditions. The dashed line corresponds to the false discovery rate of the catalog ensemble derived from the $1.91''$ seeing exposure. The high false discovery rate of the $1.91''$ seeing exposure in the low magnitude bins is due to the oversplitting of the brightest sources, as described in Figure 25. In general, the erratic false discovery rate values in the lowest magnitude bins are due to shot noise. Just as in the previous plot, I have omitted the $1.04''$ seeing and $1.92''$ seeing exposures in this plot due to the redundancy of these exposures with the $1.05''$ seeing and $1.91''$ seeing exposures, respectively. Furthermore, I have omitted the $1.14''$ seeing exposure in order to keep the plot uncluttered.

Figure 27. A plot showing completeness as a function of seeing for a range of magnitude bins beginning at 18th magnitude.

Figure 28. A nine-panel plot of an example subregion showing catalog ensembles derived from exposures with a range of seeing conditions. The background images are the same as the panels in Figure 24: each background image corresponds to the exposure with a seeing value equal to the value reported in the title. The pixel values are all in units of ADU. The red \times markers with opacity values of 1% correspond to sources from the stacked catalog ensemble, blue $+$ markers correspond to sources from the DAOPHOT catalog *derived from the 1.05'' seeing exposure*, lime green $+$ markers correspond to HST sources brighter than 22nd magnitude, and forest green $+$ markers correspond to HST sources between 22nd and 25th magnitudes. The area of each marker scales with the underlying source flux. Furthermore, the sizes of the $+$ markers are scaled with the sizes of the \times markers such that if a $+$ marker and an \times marker enclose the same area, then they represent sources of the same flux. *This figure is 300 DPI and should support high magnification using any PDF viewer.*

Figure 29. An analogous figure to Figure 28 for a different subregion of the image. The pixel values are all in units of ADU.

Figure 30. An analogous figure to Figure 28 for a different subregion of the image. The pixel values are all in units of ADU.

Figure 31. An analogous figure to Figure 28 for a different subregion of the image. The pixel values are all in units of ADU.

10. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

In this thesis, I have presented the first successful application of probabilistic cataloging to real optical data. Using a 100×100 pixel cutout of an SDSS r -band image of the globular cluster M2, I have compared the performance of probabilistic cataloging to that of DAOPHOT, the most accurate of the traditional stellar photometry packages in the crowded limit (Becker et al. 2007). By using an HST catalog of the same region of M2 as a proxy for the true stellar population, I have quantitatively shown that probabilistic cataloging produces catalogs that better represent the true stellar population: the catalog ensemble produced using probabilistic cataloging probes over 1 magnitude deeper in completeness than does the DAOPHOT catalog, while maintaining a similar false discovery rate. In order to supplement these two metrics, I have also presented extensive analysis of four subregions of the image, which contain examples of concrete situations in which probabilistic cataloging more faithfully captures the true stellar population. In addition, I have shown that probabilistic cataloging is robust to different seeing conditions, producing a catalog ensemble derived from a $1.35''$ seeing exposure that has a completeness of over half a magnitude greater than that of the DAOPHOT catalog derived from a $1.05''$ seeing exposure of the same field, while also maintaining a similar false discovery rate.

Furthermore, I have introduced a labeling procedure for distilling the catalog ensemble to a single “condensed” catalog that retains fully marginalized uncertainties and covariances between neighboring sources. Significantly, analysis of the completeness and false discovery rate of this condensed catalog reveals that the labeling procedure results in minimal information loss for high prevalence stars. Like the catalog ensemble, the condensed catalog has a completeness of over 1 magnitude greater than that of the DAOPHOT catalog, while maintaining a similar false discovery rate. In addition, I have introduced a procedure for computing position and flux sigfac, condensed catalog parameters that quantify the extent to which a source has been contaminated by crowding. Moreover, I have demonstrated that cuts on the flux sigfac parameter are an effective method of eliminating spurious sources. Indeed, varying the flux sigfac cut traces out a curve in completeness-false dis-

covery rate space, and the sigfac cut can be used as a tuning parameter for achieving the desired trade-off between completeness and false discovery rate based on one’s specific science application. Thus, I have formulated a cataloging procedure that produces a catalog ensemble and a single, tunable catalog, both of which not only better represent the true stellar population but also retain fully marginalized uncertainties and covariances between neighboring sources, a feature entirely new to cataloging.

10.1. *Improving Runtime*

The primary limitation of probabilistic cataloging in its current implementation is the CPU time required to catalog an image. Probabilistic cataloging requires approximately one day of wall clock time on `fink1` to reach convergence with a 100×100 pixel SDSS image of an extremely crowded field. For a 500×500 pixel SDSS image of a sparse field, probabilistic cataloging still requires five days of wall clock time on `fink1` to reach convergence. In order to include probabilistic cataloging in a survey pipeline, the runtime would have to be reduced by many orders of magnitude.⁵⁰ However, this implementation of probabilistic cataloging was developed as a proof of concept and does *not* achieve optimal runtime. In particular, the Finkbeiner group is currently exploring two promising areas for improving computational speed:

1. The model image evaluation, which is the current bottleneck for each step in the chain, can be optimized for runtime. As a point of reference, the model image evaluation for several hundred sources on a 100×100 pixel image using a 25×25 pixel PSF that has been upsampled by $5 \times$ currently requires approximately 100 ms on `fink1`.
2. Smarter prior and proposal distributions can be adopted in order to reach convergence in fewer steps. In such a case, the chain can also be thinned by a much smaller factor.

Initial tests suggest that the model image evaluation can be reduced by a factor of 100 by utilizing CBLAS routines in the Intel Math Kernel Library (MKL), a library of rou-

⁵⁰ The SDSS pipeline processes approximately one image per minute.

tines optimized for performance on Intel processors. In particular, the Level 3 routine `cblas_sgemm` performs optimized matrix multiplication and is callable from both C and C++. The fast matrix multiplication can be leveraged according to the following procedure.

Consider a 25×25 pixel SDSS PSF that has been upsampled by a factor of 5 using sinc interpolation, yielding a 125×125 array. We pad this array such that the last column and row are repeated, resulting in a 126×126 array. For each original pixel i of the image, we then fit a 2 variable, degree 3 polynomial to a 6×6 block consisting of the 5×5 block of the 125×125 array corresponding to pixel i , as well as the adjacent row and column.⁵¹ This polynomial fit can be accomplished using a matrix inversion and only has to be performed once, *not* every time the model image is evaluated. For each pixel i , this polynomial fit yields the coefficients $a_{i,k}$, $1 \leq k \leq 10$, of the following polynomial:

$$a_{i,1} + a_{i,2}x + a_{i,3}y + a_{i,4}x^2 + a_{i,5}xy + a_{i,6}y^2 + a_{i,7}x^3 + a_{i,8}x^2y + a_{i,9}xy^2 + a_{i,10}y^3$$

Let n be the number of sources in the catalog. For each source j , $1 \leq j \leq n$, with coordinates (x_j, y_j) , we then define:

$$dx_j = x_j - \lfloor x_j \rfloor, \quad dy_j = y_j - \lfloor y_j \rfloor$$

The pixel values of the contribution of n sources is then given by the matrix multiplication:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} & \cdots & a_{1,8} & a_{1,9} & a_{1,10} \\ a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} & \cdots & a_{2,8} & a_{2,9} & a_{2,10} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_{625,1} & a_{625,2} & a_{625,3} & \cdots & a_{625,8} & a_{625,9} & a_{625,10} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} f_1 & f_2 & \cdots & f_n \\ f_1 dx_1 & f_2 dx_2 & \cdots & f_n dx_n \\ f_1 dy_1 & f_2 dy_2 & \cdots & f_n dy_n \\ f_1 dx_1^2 & f_2 dx_2^2 & \cdots & f_n dx_n^2 \\ f_1 dx_1 dy_1 & f_2 dx_2 dy_2 & \cdots & f_n dx_n dy_n \\ f_1 dy_1^2 & f_2 dy_2^2 & \cdots & f_n dy_n^2 \\ f_1 dx_1^3 & f_2 dx_2^3 & \cdots & f_n dx_n^3 \\ f_1 dx_1^2 dy_1 & f_2 dx_2^2 dy_2 & \cdots & f_n dx_n^2 dy_n \\ f_1 dx_1 dy_1^2 & f_2 dx_2 dy_2^2 & \cdots & f_n dx_n dy_n^2 \\ f_1 dy_1^3 & f_2 dy_2^3 & \cdots & f_n dy_n^3 \end{pmatrix}$$

⁵¹ This is done so that the polynomial fit better overlaps with adjacent pixels.

where f_j is the flux of the j th source, and the i, j th entry of the resulting $625 \times n$ matrix is of the form:

$$a_{i,1} + a_{i,2}dx_j + a_{i,3}dy_j + a_{i,4}dx_j^2 + a_{i,5}dx_jdy_j + a_{i,6}dy_j^2 + a_{i,7}dx_j^3 + a_{i,8}dx_j^2dy_j + a_{i,9}dx_jdy_j^2 + a_{i,10}dy_j^3$$

This is precisely the value of the i th PSF pixel evaluated for the j th source. The 25×25 pixel contribution of each source is then added to the model image by centering the 25×25 pixel contribution for source j on $(\lfloor x_j \rfloor, \lfloor y_j \rfloor)$. This is then repeated for all j , $1 \leq j \leq n$.⁵²

Because the polynomial fit matrix inversion only needs to be performed once, it is clear that there are two potential computational bottlenecks: the matrix multiplication and the placement of each of the source contributions onto the model image. For 500 stars and a 100×100 pixel image, initial tests in C suggest that this matrix multiplication requires approximately 0.4 ms using the `cblas_sgemm` routine, and the placement of all 500 25×25 arrays onto the model image requires approximately 0.2 ms. Thus, performing the model image evaluation in C using `cblas_sgemm` reduces the model image evaluation time by a factor of approximately 100.

The second area in which the runtime can be improved is with choices of smarter prior and proposal distributions. As described in Chapters 3 and 4, the current implementation of probabilistic cataloging depends on `DNest3`, Brendon Brewer's C++ package for Diffusive Nested Sampling, which is disadvantageous for two reasons. First, Diffusive Nested Sampling is not as well studied as Metropolis-Hastings, and consequently, it is more difficult to assess convergence and identify bottlenecks in runtime. Second, the functional forms of the proposal distributions are for the most part fixed, thereby limiting the exploration of alternative proposal distributions, which is particularly important for identifying runtime improvements. Consequently, future work entails writing our own Metropolis-Hastings implementation of probabilistic cataloging in Python that utilizes the aforementioned C code for model evaluation.

⁵² Cases in which part of the 25×25 pixel array runs off the edge of the image can be handled a number of ways, the simplest of which entails padding the model image array with extra rows and columns.

With a new code base, potential modifications to the proposal distribution and prior distribution include:

1. Modifying the distribution of proposals that perturb multiple positions or fluxes simultaneously so that a high fraction of such proposals perturb sources only within a few PSF FWHMs of one another. Indeed, there is a higher probability of proposals being accepted in the case that covariant sources are perturbed simultaneously, rather than separately.
2. Perturbing a source's position and flux such that the perturbations scale with the source's uncertainty in position and flux, respectively. Derivations of the theoretical uncertainty of an isolated source of a given flux in a sparse field are given in Sections 11.4 and 11.5 in the Appendix. Though crowding affects the true uncertainties of sources,⁵³ these values can still be adopted as estimates of the optimal characteristic scales for position and flux perturbations for a given source.
3. Fixing f_{max} instead of floating it as a parameter, as described in Section 4.2.
4. Making the prior on the isotropic background parameter I_{sky} tighter, as described in Section 4.2. A more informative prior on I_{sky} would be particularly beneficial because any step perturbing I_{sky} requires the entire likelihood to be re-calculated.
5. Further exploring the effect of the prior on `norm`.⁵⁴ The prior on `norm` has a significant effect on convergence time that we do not yet fully understand. This was discovered while testing the different seeing conditions presented in Chapter 9. Because the flux distribution is fixed on the bright end by the high σ sources, `norm` in effect controls the number of sources in the fit.⁵⁵ This could be one potential cause of the prior on `norm`'s impact on convergence time. Further tests must be done in order to determine the optimal prior on `norm` in regard to convergence time.

⁵³ Indeed, this motivated `sigfac`.

⁵⁴ `norm` is equal to $dN/d \log f$.

⁵⁵ In this regard, `norm`, f_{min} , and the penalty in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source are all highly related.

10.2. Other Future Work

Of course, there are many avenues of future work to explore other than improvements to runtime. As described in Section 5.3, the 100×100 pixel cutout of M2 was chosen in part because it is free of galaxies, and probabilistic cataloging in its current implementation can only fit point sources. Indeed, in the sparse field validation described in Section 11.2 of the Appendix, the galaxies were removed by hand in order to validate the stellar photometry. However, because most stellar fields also contain galaxies, we would like to develop probabilistic cataloging so that it can differentiate between point sources and extended sources, as well as fit the extended sources. In a field with both stars and galaxies, fitting both the point sources and extended sources would be necessary to compute fully marginalized uncertainties. Indeed, fitting extended sources would prove essential if probabilistic cataloging were to be incorporated into a survey pipeline.

Another aspect of probabilistic cataloging left for future work is incorporating multi-band photometry. For my Astronomy 98 project, I attempted this using a previous implementation of probabilistic cataloging and DECam data. However, given the substantial improvements made to probabilistic cataloging over the past year, multi-band photometry with this current implementation is a next logical step. Additional future work includes:

1. Running tests that evaluate the full Poisson likelihood, as described in Section 4.3, and determining the extent to which the resulting catalog ensemble improves. This would enable us to assess the trade-off between computational speed and cataloging fidelity made with the approximations in Section 4.3.
2. Creating rigorous tests for convergence. As described in Section 4.6, it may be possible to create a generalized Gelman and Rubin convergence diagnostic for the sources in the condensed catalog.
3. Deriving a theoretically-motivated optimal choice of f_{min} . As described in Section 11.1 of the Appendix, the primary method by which f_{min} was selected for this thesis was empirical testing.

4. Determining the optimal penalty in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source. In Section 4.2, I provided theoretical motivation for a penalty of $3/2$, and in Section 11.1 of the Appendix, I empirically tested this value, as well as a penalty of 0. However, a rigorous method for choosing the optimal value of the penalty in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source is left for future work.
5. Determining the optimal values of flux and position sigfac cuts. One could theoretically determine the sigfac cuts that correspond to optimal values in a receiver operating characteristic curve, such as the one in Figure 23, by maximizing the F1 score from binary classification literature. However, it is worth noting that different sigfac cuts may be adopted based on the specific science application: some applications may require a clean sample, and others may require greater completeness.
6. Understanding prevalence as a tuning parameter for the condensed catalog. Unlike sigfac, we have not yet developed a comprehensive enough understanding of the theoretical underpinnings of prevalence to use it as a meaningful method of eliminating spurious sources from the catalog.

In regard to future work directly related to the specific M2 field chosen for analysis in this thesis, there is one primary avenue left to explore. Because there is a 5% mismatch between the PSF provided by the SDSS pipeline and the true PSF of the image, it would be beneficial to test runs in which a 5% error term is incorporated into the likelihood in equation (36):

$$\log \mathcal{L} \approx - \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2[\lambda_{lm} + (0.05S_{lm})^2]} + C' \quad (38)$$

It is possible that probabilistic cataloging would perform better on the test image with this error term added.

10.3. *Toward Future Survey Pipelines*

As demonstrated by this thesis, probabilistic cataloging has two primary advantages over traditional stellar photometry packages such as DAOPHOT:

1. For a 100×100 pixel cutout of an SDSS r -band image of M2, probabilistic cataloging goes over 1 magnitude deeper in completeness than does DAOPHOT while maintaining a similar false discovery rate up to 20th magnitude. Significantly, because DAOPHOT is the most robust of the traditional stellar photometry packages in the crowded limit, outperforming DAOPHOT is equivalent to outperforming all traditional stellar photometry packages (Becker et al. 2007).
2. The catalog ensemble and condensed catalog retain fully marginalized uncertainties and covariances between neighbors, a feature entirely new to stellar photometry packages.

The primary barrier to including this current implementation of probabilistic cataloging in future survey pipelines is its runtime. However, as discussed in the previous sections, it is reasonable to believe that a 2-3 order of magnitude improvement in runtime can be accomplished with relatively little code development and smarter choices for the proposal and prior distributions. Furthermore, one can expect additional substantial reductions in CPU runtime over the next decade due to Moore’s Law and the exponential rise in computing power. Given that probabilistic cataloging probes over 1 magnitude deeper in the crowded limit and that CPU time is more cost effective than telescope time, the aforementioned runtime improvements may suffice for the inclusion of probabilistic cataloging in future survey pipelines in order to maximize information gain as a function of survey cost.

As telescope depth continues to improve, a higher fraction of images will be in the crowded limit, placing even more importance on crowded field photometry. Indeed, no current photometry package is sufficient for future surveys: according to Becker et al. (2007), none of the traditional stellar photometry packages meet the LSST pipeline requirements.

Thus, the need for accurate crowded field photometry is greater than ever. With improvements, probabilistic cataloging could very well be the answer.

11. APPENDIX

11.1. *Determining f_{min}*

f_{min} is a necessary feature of probabilistic cataloging because $f_{min} = 0$ would allow the fit to place an arbitrary number of faint sources (up to N_{max}) in order to produce a model image that reproduces the observed image to an arbitrary degree of accuracy. Unlike the other parameters described in Section 4.5, f_{min} raises a subtle question: how does this minimum bound on source flux in probabilistic cataloging differ from the minimum σ cut imposed by DAOPHOT?⁵⁶ Ostensibly, f_{min} imposes the precise condition that probabilistic cataloging is supposed to circumvent. However, f_{min} differs in a significant way: the chain can still identify a source with a true flux less than f_{min} , as long as the chain assigns the source a flux value of f_{min} or greater. For sources with fluxes just below f_{min} , this effect is negligible. In this regard, the chain has more flexibility with faint source detection than does DAOPHOT.

Of course, it is still instructive to consider different cases of f_{min} and test probabilistic cataloging's response to the tuning parameters presented in Section 4.5. Accordingly, I present a comparison of runs with different values of f_{min} , as well as different penalties in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source. Though I have already provided motivation for the choices of $f_{min} = 250$ and a penalty of $3/2$ in log likelihood for the addition of a new source, it is nonetheless instructive to justify these choices with empirical evidence as well. In particular, runs with four different configurations were tested:

1. $f_{min} = 250$ ADU (corresponding to 22nd magnitude) and a penalty of $3/2$ in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source
2. $f_{min} = 100$ ADU (corresponding to 23rd magnitude) and a penalty of $3/2$ in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source
3. $f_{min} = 40$ ADU (corresponding to 24th magnitude) and a penalty of $3/2$ in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source

⁵⁶ This σ cut is described in Section 2.4.

4. $f_{min} = 250$ ADU and no penalty in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source

In this case, it is most instructive to consider the corresponding catalog ensembles for sample subregions of the image, as it is difficult to quantify some of these effects and is easier to identify them by eye in a qualitative fashion. In Figures 32, 33, 34, and 35, I present four such subregions, the same subregions used in Sections 6.3 and 7.1.

Of primary interest is the optimal value of f_{min} , such that the sources in the catalog ensemble best represent the true source population. As expected, lowering f_{min} increases the number of sources introduced in the catalog ensemble. As can be seen in the figures, the catalog ensembles from the $f_{min} = 40$ and “no penalty” runs contain many spurious sources, in that they do not have corresponding HST sources. The $f_{min} = 100$ catalog ensemble does not suffer from this phenomenon as noticeably. In fact, in some cases, the $f_{min} = 100$ catalog ensemble better constrains HST sources in comparison to the $f_{min} = 250$ catalog ensemble, as evidenced by the source located at (70, 56) in Figure 32. In isolated incidents, the $f_{min} = 100$ catalog ensemble even identifies sources that were undetected by the $f_{min} = 250$ catalog ensemble, as is the case with HST sources at (70, 54) in Figure 32.

However, the differences in the $f_{min} = 100$ catalog ensemble are not entirely beneficial: for example, the HST source at (66, 35) in Figure 33 is more localized in the $f_{min} = 250$ catalog ensemble than in the $f_{min} = 100$ catalog ensemble. Examples such as these are present in all four figures. In addition, the $f_{min} = 100$ catalog ensemble contains a number of spurious sources not contained in the $f_{min} = 250$ catalog ensemble. For these reasons, I have selected the $f_{min} = 250$ run as the optimal run completed thus far and have adopted it as the primary run for the purposes of this thesis. However, it is important to acknowledge that the problem of identifying the true optimal value of f_{min} is a non-trivial one that has not yet been solved. For this reason, this problem is left for future work.

Figure 32. A sample region showing the results of four runs with different settings: $f_{min} = 250$ (corresponding to 22nd magnitude), $f_{min} = 100$ (corresponding to 23rd magnitude), $f_{min} = 40$ (corresponding to 24th magnitude), and $f_{min} = 250$ with no penalty in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source. Just as in Figures 7, 8, 9, and 10, the red \times markers with opacity values of 1% correspond to sources from the stacked catalog ensemble, blue $+$ markers correspond to sources from the DAOPHOT catalog, lime green $+$ markers correspond to HST sources brighter than 22nd magnitude, and forest green $+$ markers correspond to HST sources between 22nd and 25th magnitude. The area of each marker scales with the flux of the inferred source that it represents. The sizes of the ‘+’ markers are scaled with the sizes of the ‘ \times ’ markers such that if a ‘+’ marker and an ‘ \times ’ marker enclose the same area, then they represent sources of the same flux. The background image is the observed SDSS image. The pixel values are all in units of ADU. *This figure is 300 DPI and should support high magnification using any PDF viewer.*

Figure 33. An analogous figure to Figure 32 for a different sample region of the image. The pixel values are all in units of ADU.

Figure 34. An analogous figure to Figure 32 for a different sample region of the image. The pixel values are all in units of ADU.

Figure 35. An analogous figure to Figure 32 for a different sample region of the image. The pixel values are all in units of ADU.

11.2. Sparse Field Validation of Probabilistic Cataloging

Any analysis of a cataloging method would be incomplete without a validation that the method performs accurate astrometry and photometry on a sparse field. This is of particular importance in this instance because the HST catalog photometry cannot be used to validate probabilistic cataloging photometry due to the differences between the HST F606W filter and the SDSS r -band filter, as described in Section 5.3. Fortunately, tests on a sparse field can be used to validate the photometry of probabilistic cataloging to the hundredth of a magnitude level: catalogs produced using the SDSS `Photo` package can be taken as ground truth for sparse fields, and probabilistic cataloging can be run on the very same sparse field SDSS r -band images. Of course, the astrometry of probabilistic cataloging can also be validated for good measure.

In order to run this test, we selected a 500×500 pixel cutout of the SDSS r -band image of M2 from Data Release 12 with the following identification numbers in the SDSS Data Release 12 pipeline: run 2583, field 134, camcol 2 (Alam et al. 2015). We extracted this 500×500 pixel region and the SDSS pipeline-generated PSF, as well as the gain, bias, and counts-to-nanomaggies conversion, according to the procedure described at the end of Section 5.2. This field is located just outside of the M2 cluster and was taken from the same run and camcol as the 100×100 pixel crowded field test image. Because this field is quite sparse,⁵⁷ the SDSS pipeline photometry package `Photo` did successfully run and produce a catalog, as desired. The probabilistic cataloging run was set with an $f_{min} = 250$ and a penalty of $3/2$ in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source. Furthermore, this run required 5 days of wall clock time to converge.

Unlike the 100×100 pixel crowded field test image analyzed in the other chapters, a high fraction of sources in this 500×500 pixel sparse field image are galaxies. Because this implementation of probabilistic cataloging does not differentiate extended sources from point sources and instead treats all sources as point sources, I restrict the analysis to sources identified in the corresponding `Photo` catalog as point sources.

⁵⁷ The 100×100 pixel crowded field image has approximately $10^3 \times$ the number of sources per pixel.

In this image, `Photo` identified 40 point sources. All 40 of these `Photo` sources were identified by the catalog ensemble. The catalog ensemble suffers from some minor oversplitting effects. In order to compensate for this effect, the constituent fluxes of oversplit sources have been added together in the following analysis, and the mean source position of each oversplit source is taken to be a weighted average of constituent positions according to flux. The question of whether to merge sources due to oversplitting was unambiguous for all of these cases.

In Figure 36, I present plots of the differential positions in both coordinates as functions of `Photo` magnitude.⁵⁸ The majority of positions are constrained to well within 0.1 pixels. In Figure 37, I present a plot of the differential magnitudes of these stars as a function of SDSS r magnitude.⁵⁸ At 16th magnitude, the magnitudes are constrained to within 0.015 magnitudes, and at 20th magnitude, the magnitudes are constrained to within 0.09 magnitudes. Though there are inherent limitations on the lower bounds of uncertainty, one would hope to constrain all of the magnitudes to the hundredth of a magnitude level. We are currently exploring the magnitude differential present in these results. Determining the cause of this is left for future work. Regardless, the probabilistic cataloging photometry and astrometry are performing to a high degree of accuracy and thus have been validated in the sparse field case, as desired.

⁵⁸ This figure was made by Stephen Portillo.

Figure 36. A two-panel plot of the differential x & y positions of the matched sources as functions of `Photo r` magnitude. The probabilistic cataloging position of a source is taken to be the mean position of the source across all samples from the catalog ensemble. The error bars correspond to 1σ uncertainty across the catalog samples in the ensemble. This plot was made by Stephen Portillo.

Figure 37. A plot of the differential magnitudes of the matched sources as a function of `Photo r` magnitude. The probabilistic cataloging magnitude of a source is taken to be the mean magnitude of the source across all samples from the catalog ensemble. The error bars correspond to 1σ uncertainty across the catalog samples in the ensemble. This plot was made by Stephen Portillo.

11.3. Convergence Statistics

In this section, I report statistics related to the convergence of the central run adopted for this thesis, a run on a $1.05''$ seeing exposure set with $f_{min} = 250$ and a penalty of $3/2$ in log likelihood for the introduction of a new source. In Figure 38, I present a histogram of the pixel value residuals for the 300 samples in the catalog ensemble. As seen in the figure, the histogram is a normal distribution with a mean at 0.59 ADU. In Figure 39, I present an analogous histogram of the isotropic background I_{sky} . The distribution is contained within $\pm 1\%$ of 1223 ADU. Thus, as described in Section 4.2, the chain does not brush against the minimum and maximum allowed values of 300 ADU and 3000 ADU, respectively.

In Figure 40, I present a histogram of the number of sources per catalog for the 300 samples in the catalog ensemble. Significantly, the distribution does not appear to be a normal distribution, as one would expect in the sparse field limit. However, it is important to remember that neighboring sources are extremely covariant with one another in this crowded field, and consequently, the decision to add or remove a source has an appreciable impact on the presence of neighboring sources. Phrased alternatively, two catalogs differing in the number of contained sources could nonetheless describe the true stellar population equally well in the crowded limit. Thus, the lack of a normal distribution in Figure 40 should *not* be taken as an indication of poor convergence.

Lastly, as described in Section 4.6, the Gelman and Rubin convergence diagnostic can be applied to the pixel values. Of course, it is necessary to have multiple runs in order to compute the inter-chain variance. For this purpose, I compare this run to the $1.05''$ seeing exposure run used for analysis in Chapter 9. This run, too, was set with $f_{min} = 250$ and a penalty of $3/2$ for the introduction of a new source. In Figure 41, I present a histogram of the potential scale reduction factor (PSRF) values for each of the $10,000$ pixels. There is a high concentration of PSRF values very close to 1 , as desired.

Figure 38. A histogram of the residuals of all 300 samples in the catalog ensemble, calculated as observed minus model. Because there are 10,000 pixels per model image, there are 3,000,000 datapoints in total.

Figure 39. A histogram of the isotropic background for 300 samples in the catalog ensemble.

Figure 40. A histogram of the number of sources for each of the 300 catalogs in the catalog ensemble.

Figure 41. A histogram of the PSRF values of the 10,000 pixels, as calculated using the Gelman and Rubin convergence diagnostic for two runs on the $1.05''$ seeing exposure, each with $f_{min} = 250$ and a penalty of $3/2$ for the introduction of a new source.

11.4. Derivation of Flux Sigfac

In this section, I present a derivation of the flux sigfac for the condensed catalog. This derivation follows analogously to the derivation presented in Appendix C of [Portillo et al. \(2017\)](#), with intermediate steps in the derivation added here for clarity. We begin with the approximation made in equation (36):

$$\log \mathcal{L} \approx - \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2\lambda_{lm}} \quad (39)$$

We then consider an isolated source with a maximum likelihood flux of f_* . Assuming that the likelihood dominates over the prior and that the position of the given source, as well as the positions and fluxes of neighboring sources and nuisance parameters, are well-constrained, f_* can be found by maximizing the likelihood, which is equivalent to maximizing the log likelihood:

$$\left. \frac{\partial \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f} \right|_{f=f_*} = 0 \quad (40)$$

We can then determine the flux variance about the maximum likelihood:

$$\sigma_f^2 = \langle (f - f_*)^2 \rangle = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp(\log \mathcal{L}) (f - f_*)^2 df}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp(\log \mathcal{L}) df} \quad (41)$$

Taylor expanding the log likelihood about f_* , we find that:

$$\log \mathcal{L}|_f = \log \mathcal{L}|_{f=f_*} + \left. \frac{\partial \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f} \right|_{f=f_*} (f - f_*) + \frac{1}{2} \left. \frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f^2} \right|_{f=f_*} (f - f_*)^2 + \mathcal{O}[(f - f_*)^3] \quad (42)$$

Using equation (40) and truncating the expansion at second order, we find that:

$$\log \mathcal{L}|_f \approx \log \mathcal{L}|_{f=f_*} + \frac{1}{2} \left. \frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f^2} \right|_{f=f_*} (f - f_*)^2 \quad (43)$$

Substituting this into equation (41), we find that:

$$\sigma_f^2 \approx \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp\left(\log \mathcal{L}|_{f=f_*} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f^2} \Big|_{f=f_*} (f-f_*)^2\right) (f-f_*)^2 df}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp\left(\log \mathcal{L}|_{f=f_*} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f^2} \Big|_{f=f_*} (f-f_*)^2\right) df} = \left(-\frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f^2} \Big|_{f=f_*}\right)^{-1} \quad (44)$$

As motivated by equation (33), under the assumption that the source is isolated in the sparse field, the model flux is given by:

$$\lambda_{lm} \approx I_{sky} + f \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y) \quad (45)$$

We find that:

$$\frac{\partial \lambda_{lm}}{\partial f} = \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y) \quad (46)$$

We then take the first and second partial derivatives $\log \mathcal{L}$ with respect to f using the chain rule and equation (36):

$$\frac{\partial \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f} = \frac{\partial \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial \lambda_{lm}} \frac{\partial \lambda_{lm}}{\partial f} = \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_{lm}} \left(-\sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2\lambda_{lm}} \right) \right] \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y) \quad (47)$$

Evaluating the partial, we find that:

$$\frac{\partial \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f} = - \left[\sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left(-\frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2\lambda_{lm}^2} + 1 - \frac{k_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y) \right] \quad (48)$$

We can then evaluate the second partial by another application of the chain rule:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f^2} &= \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_{lm}} \left(\frac{\partial \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f} \right) \right] \frac{\partial \lambda_{lm}}{\partial f} \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_{lm}} \left[-\sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left(-\frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2\lambda_{lm}^2} + 1 - \frac{k_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y) \right] \right) \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y) \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

which yields:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f^2} = - \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left[\left(\frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{\lambda_{lm}^3} + \frac{2(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})}{\lambda_{lm}^2} + \frac{1}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \mathcal{P}^2(l-x, m-y) \right] \quad (50)$$

and in turn simplifies to:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f^2} \approx - \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \frac{\mathcal{P}^2(l-x, m-y)}{\lambda_{lm}} \left(1 + \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right)^2 \quad (51)$$

Under the assumption that:

$$\frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \ll 1 \quad (52)$$

we arrive at the expression:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial f^2} \approx - \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \frac{\mathcal{P}^2(l-x, m-y)}{I_{sky} + f \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y)} \quad (53)$$

Substituting this into equation (44), we find that:

$$\sigma_f^2 \approx \left(\sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \frac{\mathcal{P}^2(l-x, m-y)}{I_{sky} + f_* \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y)} \right)^{-1} \quad (54)$$

The flux sigfac is thus given by the uncertainty in flux reported in the condensed catalog, divided by the value of σ_f from equation (54). With a noise floor of 1% added to account for phenomena such as a PSF mismatch, this proves to be in agreement with the results, as presented in Section 7.2.

11.5. Derivation of Position Sigfac

Without loss of generality, we derive σ_x . We consider an isolated source with a maximum likelihood x -position x_* . Assuming that the likelihood dominates over the prior and that the y -position and flux of the given source, as well as the positions and fluxes of neighboring sources and nuisance parameters, are well-constrained, x_* can be found by maximizing the likelihood, which is equivalent to maximizing the log likelihood:

$$\left. \frac{\partial \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial x} \right|_{x=x_*} = 0 \quad (55)$$

We can then determine the flux variance about the maximum likelihood:

$$\sigma_x^2 = \langle (x-x_*)^2 \rangle = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp(\log \mathcal{L})(x-x_*)^2 dx}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp(\log \mathcal{L}) dx} \quad (56)$$

Taylor expanding the log likelihood about x_* , we find that:

$$\log \mathcal{L}|_x = \log \mathcal{L}|_{x=x_*} + \left. \frac{\partial \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial x} \right|_{x=x_*} (x-x_*) + \frac{1}{2} \left. \frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial x^2} \right|_{x=x_*} (x-x_*)^2 + \mathcal{O}[(x-x_*)^3] \quad (57)$$

Using equation (40) and truncating the expansion at second order, we find that:

$$\log \mathcal{L}|_f \approx \log \mathcal{L}|_{x=x_*} + \frac{1}{2} \left. \frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial x^2} \right|_{x=x_*} (x-x_*)^2 \quad (58)$$

Substituting this into equation (56), we find that:

$$\sigma_x^2 \approx \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp \left(\log \mathcal{L}|_{x=x_*} + \frac{1}{2} \left. \frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial x^2} \right|_{x=x_*} (x-x_*)^2 \right) (x-x_*)^2 dx}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp \left(\log \mathcal{L}|_{x=x_*} + \frac{1}{2} \left. \frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial x^2} \right|_{x=x_*} (x-x_*)^2 \right) dx} = \left(- \left. \frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial x^2} \right|_{x=x_*} \right)^{-1} \quad (59)$$

As motivated by equation (33), under the assumption that the source is isolated in the sparse field, the model flux is given by:

$$\lambda_{lm} \approx I_{sky} + f_* \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \quad (60)$$

where here the y -position and flux of the star are y_* and f_* , as they are fixed. We find that:

$$\frac{\partial \lambda_{lm}}{\partial x} = f_* \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \quad (61)$$

We then take the first and second partial derivatives $\log \mathcal{L}$ with respect to f using the chain rule and equation (36):

$$\frac{\partial \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial \lambda_{lm}} \frac{\partial \lambda_{lm}}{\partial x} = \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_{lm}} \left(- \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2\lambda_{lm}} \right) \right] f_* \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \quad (62)$$

Evaluating the partial, we find that:

$$\frac{\partial \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial x} = -f_* \left[\sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left(- \frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2\lambda_{lm}^2} + 1 - \frac{k_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right] \quad (63)$$

We can then evaluate the second partial by another application of the chain rule:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial x^2} &= \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_{lm}} \left(\frac{\partial \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial x} \right) \right] \frac{\partial \lambda_{lm}}{\partial x} \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_{lm}} \left[-f_* \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left(- \frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2\lambda_{lm}^2} + 1 - \frac{k_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y) \right] \right) f_* \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

We find that:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_{lm}} \left[-f_* \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left(-\frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2\lambda_{lm}^2} + 1 - \frac{k_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right] \\
&= -f_* \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left[\left(\frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{\lambda_{lm}^3} + \frac{2(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})}{\lambda_{lm}^2} + \frac{1}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \left(-\frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2\lambda_{lm}^2} + 1 - \frac{k_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_{lm}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right] \\
&= -f_* \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_{lm}} \left(1 + \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right)^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) + \left(-\frac{(k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm})^2}{2\lambda_{lm}^2} + 1 - \frac{k_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_{lm}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right] \\
&= -f_* \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_{lm}} \left(1 + \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right)^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) - \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_{lm}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right] \\
&= -f_* \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_{lm}} \left(1 + \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right)^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) - \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \frac{\partial x}{\partial \lambda_{lm}} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right] \\
&= -f_* \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_{lm}} \left(1 + \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right)^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \left(\frac{1}{f_* \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*)} \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right] \quad (65)
\end{aligned}$$

and thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial x^2} &= -f_*^2 \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_{lm}} \left(1 + \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right)^2 \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \left(\frac{1}{f_*} \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right] \\
&= -f_*^2 \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \frac{1}{\lambda_{lm}} \left[\left(1 + \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right)^2 - \right. \\
&\quad \left. \frac{\lambda_{lm} k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{f_* \lambda_{lm}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right] \quad (66)
\end{aligned}$$

As with the flux sigfac derivation, we make the assumption that:

$$\frac{k_{lm} - \lambda_{lm}}{\lambda_{lm}} \ll 1 \quad (67)$$

Here, we also make the assumption that λ_{lm}/f_* is small. Thus, we find that:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \log \mathcal{L}}{\partial x^2} &\approx -f_*^2 \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_{lm}} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right)^2 \right] \\ &= -f_*^2 \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left[\frac{1}{I_{sky} + f_* \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*)} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right)^2 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

Substituting this into equation (59), we find that:

$$\sigma_x^2 \approx \frac{1}{f_*^2} \left\{ \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left[\frac{1}{I_{sky} + f_* \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*)} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathcal{P}(l-x, m-y_*) \right)^2 \right] \right\}^{-1} \quad (69)$$

σ_y is defined analogously:

$$\sigma_y^2 \approx \frac{1}{f_*^2} \left\{ \sum_{l=1}^W \sum_{m=1}^H \left[\frac{1}{I_{sky} + f_* \mathcal{P}(l-x_*, m-y)} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mathcal{P}(l-x_*, m-y) \right)^2 \right] \right\}^{-1} \quad (70)$$

We then define the position error σ_{pos} by adding σ_x and σ_y in quadrature:

$$\sigma_{pos} = \sqrt{\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2} \quad (71)$$

The position sigfac is thus given by the uncertainty in position reported in the condensed catalog (calculated by adding the uncertainties of x and y in quadrature), divided by the value of σ_{pos} from equation (71). With a noise floor of 0.5% added to account for phenomena such as a PSF mismatch, this proves to be in agreement with the results, as presented in Section 7.2.

12. SCIENCE ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The computations in this thesis were run on the Odyssey cluster supported by the FAS Division of Science, Research Computing Group at Harvard University. Furthermore, this research has made use of NASA's Astrophysics Data System. Funding for SDSS-III has been provided by the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, the Participating Institutions, the National Science Foundation, and the U.S. Department of Energy Office of Science. The SDSS-III web site is <http://www.sdss3.org/>.

SDSS-III is managed by the Astrophysical Research Consortium for the Participating Institutions of the SDSS-III Collaboration including the University of Arizona, the Brazilian Participation Group, Brookhaven National Laboratory, University of Cambridge, Carnegie Mellon University, University of Florida, the French Participation Group, the German Participation Group, Harvard University, the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias, the Michigan State/Notre Dame/JINA Participation Group, Johns Hopkins University, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, Max Planck Institute for Astrophysics, Max Planck Institute for Extraterrestrial Physics, New Mexico State University, New York University, Ohio State University, Pennsylvania State University, University of Portsmouth, Princeton University, the Spanish Participation Group, University of Tokyo, University of Utah, Vanderbilt University, University of Virginia, University of Washington, and Yale University.

REFERENCES

- Alam, S., et al. 2015, *ApJS*, 219, 12
- Albaret, F.D., et al. 2016, ArXiv e-prints, arXiv:1608.02013v1
- An, D., et al. 2008, *ApJS*, 179, 326
- Anderson, J., et al. 2008, *AJ*, 135, 6
- Annunziatella, M., Mercurio, A., Brescia, M., Cavuoti, S., & Longo, G. 2012, ArXiv e-prints, arXiv:1212.0564
- Becker, A., Silvestri, N., Owen, R., Ivezić, Ž., & Lupton, R. 2007, *PASP*, 119, 1462
- Bertin, E., & Arnouts, S. 1996, *A&AS*, 117, 393
- Brewer, B., Pártay, L., & Csányi, G. 2010, *Statistics and Computing*, 21, 649
- Brewer, B., Foreman-Mackey, D., & Hogg, D. 2013, *AJ*, 146, 1
- Brewer, B. 2015, arXiv:1411.3921
- Brewer, B. 2016. DNest3, <https://github.com/eggplantbren/DNest3>
- Brewer, B., & Foreman-Mackey, D. 2016, arXiv:1606.03757v3
- Budavári, T., & Basu, A. 2016, ArXiv e-prints, arXiv:1609.03065
- Cowles, M., & Carlin, B. 2015, *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 91, 434
- Davis, L. 1994, "A Reference Guide to the IRAF/DAOPHOT Package"
- Daylan, T., Portillo, S., & Finkbeiner, D. 2016, ArXiv e-prints, arXiv:1607.04637
- Doi, M., et al. 2010, *AJ*, 139, 4
- Eisenstein, D., et al. 2005, *ApJ*, 633, 2
- Fan, Y., & Sisson, S. 2010, arXiv:1001.2055
- Ferrarese, L., Silberman, N., Mould, J., Stetson, P., Saha, A., Freedman, W., & Kennicutt Jr., R. 2000, *PASP*, 112, 177
- Gelman, A., & Rubin D. 1992, *Statistical Science*, 7, 457
- Green, P. 1995, *Biometrika*, 82, 711
- Gunn, J.E. 1998, *AJ*, 116, 6
- Harris, W. E. 1996, *AJ*, 112, 1487
- Jiang, L., et al. 2014, *ApJS*, 213, 1
- Laher, R., et al. 2012, *PASP*, 124:737
- Lupton, R., et al. 2001, *ASP Conf. Ser.* 10, 269
- MacKay, D. 2003, *Information Theory, Inference, and Learning Algorithms* (6th ed.; Cambridge University Press)
- Portillo, S.K.N., Lee, B.C.G., Daylan, T., & Finkbeiner, D.P. 2017, arXiv:1703.01303
- Primini, F., & Kashyap, V. 2014, *ApJ*, 796, 7
- Romanishin, W. 2006, "An Introduction to Astronomical Photometry Using CCDs," http://www.physics.csbsju.edu/370/photometry/manuals/OU.edu_CCD_photometry_wrccd06.pdf

- Sambridge, M., Gallagher, K., Jackson, A., & Rickwood, P. 2006, *GeoJI*, 167, 528
- Sarajedini, A., Bedin, L. R., Chaboyer, B., et al. 2007, *AJ*, 133, 1658
- Schechter, P., Mateo, M., & Saha, A. 1993, *PASP*, 105, 1342
- Stephens, M. 2000, *Ann. Statist.*, 28, 40
- Stetson, P. 1987, *PASP*, 99, 191
- Stetson, P. 1998, "User's Manual for DAOPHOT II"
- Trotta, R. 2008, *ConPh*, 49, 71
- York, D., et al. 2000, *ApJ*, 120, 3